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PREFACE

Throughout history, humans have endeavored to comprehend the concept of death and have generated many notions on the matter. Individuals endeavor to perceive and comprehend mortality based on their own beliefs, sense of self, and the surrounding context. While some individuals embrace mortality, others actively seek immortality and refuse to accept the inevitability of death. The primary factor contributing to the challenge of comprehending death lies in its metaphysical nature and the inherent impossibility of directly experiencing it. In order to acquire more precise answers, we propose examining the phenomena of death, which cannot be empirically explored, by considering the insights of some philosophers and scientists who have drawn from Islamic sources.

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SUMMARY

The inherent inability to feel death and the lack of scientific means to test it contribute to the complexity of the matter, thereby giving rise to many hypotheses. To elucidate this matter and resolve any disputes, our research has two primary components. Initially, we conducted a comprehensive analysis of the human population as a whole, as a prerequisite for comprehending the concept of mortality. Next, we elucidate the human's conduct in relation to mortality and their profound vulnerability when confronted with the inevitability of death. Subsequently, we concluded our investigation by scrutinizing the matters pertaining to the demise and the subsequent occurrences. The phenomenon of death has been extensively studied, delineated, and attempted to be comprehended in several scientific disciplines. Across the course of history, many religious beliefs and teachings have given rise to diverse understandings and explanations about the concept of death. The topic of death has been a prominent focus for philosophers and scientists, both in the present century and throughout human history. Individuals' perspectives on mortality differ from one another and might also vary across diverse cultures. Undoubtedly, the Quran's response to the subject of death in Islam has significant importance. Additional components of the thesis will explore the connection between death and related subjects, such as existence in the grave, the apocalypse, judgment, and retribution. Individuals first undergo a condition of disfavor and astonishment when encountering death, but subsequently they acknowledge the circumstances and adjust to their existence. However, without enough expertise and equipment in this field, he may be exposed to mortal danger and experience a decline in his psychological well-being. The Holy Quran cautions individuals about mortality and mentally prepares them for the experience of death and its consequences. Mortality is a formidable challenge; however humanity has been bestowed with the capacity to triumph over this challenge by divine intervention. Initially, our study focused on analyzing the verses in the Quran that introduce and provide descriptions of human beings. In addition, we considered the perspectives of psychologists and sociologists, as well as the

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methodologies used by Islamic scholars. In the second section, we endeavored to analyze the occurrence of death, the apocalypse, the consequences of the apocalypse, and the depictions of the afterlife as described in the Holy Quran. These investigations will enhance individuals' comprehension of mortality, the purpose of their existence, and their self-perception.

Key Words: *Creation in Islam, Philosophy of Creation, Creation and Human, Human Creation, Creation According to Religions*

INTRODUCTION

FIRST PART

HUMAN AND HUMAN'S CREATION

THE CONCEPT OF HUMAN IN A UNIVERSAL SENSE

The term "human", originating from Arabic, is derived from the root "ins" and signifies "human, human being" for all people. People are said to be human because they form interpersonal connections. A human being is a social creature that relies on connections not only with other humans but also with the entire realm of existence. They are highly adaptable to living in communities, displaying qualities such as affection, friendliness, harmlessness, decency, mercy, and conscience. Additionally, humans possess intelligence, consciousness, the ability to think, communicate, and experience joy.

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THE CREATION OF HUMANS ACCORDING TO THE QURAN

The Quran presents the creation of man in a captivating manner. According to the Holy Quran, Allah affirms that He brought about the existence of all things via water and emphasizes the crucial role of water in the development of life. The Holy Quran primarily focuses on delineating the many phases and fundamental composition of human beings while discussing their formation. The scriptures discussing the creation of man indicate two distinct sorts of creation. This creation is a manifestation of divine might. Adam, the first person, was formed from a combination of earth, mud, and water, both externally and inside.

Idea of Creation

Islam acknowledges the connection between God in His role as the Creator and mankind in their capacity as His created. Muslims hold the belief that "Allah," the name denoting the divine being, is the only creator of the universe and all its constituents. A core principle of Islam is the acknowledgement that Allah is the creator of all entities in the cosmos, including mankind. According to Islamic doctrine, God brought about the existence of Adam and Eve as the first human beings and thereafter generated succeeding generations. They hold the belief that people were created by God with the purpose of worshipping Him and carrying out their responsibilities as His ambassadors on the planet. Hence, Islam establishes a strong connection between people and animals. Man was intricately fashioned by God with a certain purpose in mind. Purpose encompasses the acts of venerating and abiding by God, attaining sagacity, behaving virtuously, and properly governing the world and its resources. In Islam, there exists a profound connection between people and their creations since God mandated the creation of mankind for many objectives. This objective encompasses endeavors to uphold and adhere to the divine intentions, to

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attain wisdom, to behave virtuously, and to conscientiously oversee the Earth and its assets. According to Islamic beliefs, God is believed to have created other entities, such as angels and jinns. The animals have been allocated diverse roles as part of God's complete plan. Muslims hold the belief that God has bestowed onto humanity the faculties of reason and free choice, enabling them to carry out their responsibilities as His emissaries on the planet. In Islam, the belief in God as the ultimate creator and the understanding that people have distinct roles and objectives in the universe greatly influences the dynamic between humans and their creations. Eghbalian et al. (2022) assert that the fundamental objective of human being and creation in Islam is to have faith and believe in the oneness of Allah. Islamic doctrine posits that the primary objective of human life is to place unwavering faith in and engage in reverential devotion to the divine being. Muslims have a belief in and hold in high esteem the omnipotent God, while simultaneously matching their ideas, emotions, and actions with the objective of creation, which is the ultimate aim of human life. Muslims endeavor to lead a life characterized by complete submission to Allah, earnestly seeking His approval, and faithfully adhering to His precepts. Therefore, people have a duty not just to fulfill their obligations towards God, but also to be accountable for their actions towards society and the environment (Ousama and Fatima, 2010). In Islam, individuals have a dual duty: to fulfill their commitments towards Allah and to take responsibility for the well-being and preservation of society and the environment. In Islam, people are obligated to fulfill their duties not just towards Allah, but also towards society and the environment. Their responsibility is in ensuring the welfare and safeguarding of these assets. As to Islamic beliefs, humans are seen as custodians of God's creation, therefore bearing obligations towards both society and the environment. In Islam, there exists a significant connection between humanity and the act of creation. This link is predicated on the notion that God is the ultimate progenitor. Hence, individuals want to venerate God, adhere to His teachings, attain wisdom, exhibit virtuous conduct, and fulfill their duty as conscientious caretakers of the earth. In Islam, which is founded on the belief in the supremacy of Allah as the creator, there exists a significant connection between humanity and the natural world. According to this perspective, the primary objectives of humanity are to engage in the worship of God, adhere

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to obedience, seek knowledge, exhibit virtuous behavior, and fulfill the role of responsible caretakers of the planet. In Islam, there exists an inherent connection between people and animals, which originates from the belief that humans possess an innate purpose of worship, and that Allah is the ultimate creator.

Stages of Creation of Man from Soil.

1- The first substance in human creation is soil.

2- Soil has gone through some phases as a result of its interaction with air and water. Mud, sticky slime, sappy slime, essence filtered from mud, dry mud, and shaped dry mud... Human beings carry within themselves the elements that the earth contains. However, although the elements in this mud are known, it is not known how it came to form the first organic life.

3- God breathed his own spirit into man, and with this stage the creation of man was completed.

Stages of Creation of Man in the Womb.

1- Man was created from water.

2- The stages that the living life form, consisting of elements mixed with water, has gone through.

Man was created from thrown water. That water comes out between the waist and ribcage. Nutfe (sperm-fertilized egg) is referred to as an adulterated sperm . Then there is the formation of the object that sticks to the uterine wall, the thing that is suspended in the uterus and fed, then the shapeless piece of chewed meat, and then the skeletal and muscular system. After all these stages, the human being turns into a perfect organism.

PURPOSE OF HUMAN CREATION

Human beings, who were created by Allah in a supremely exquisite and faultless manner, were appointed as the representatives of Allah on Earth and attained the utmost rank among all living beings. Due to their unique status, people possess several rights and obligations. In the following verses, Allah elucidates that man was not fashioned in an absolutely flawless manner. "Does an individual believe that they will be abandoned?" and "Did you assume that We brought you into existence without purpose and that you would never be returned to Us?" These passages illustrate the many responsibilities that mankind have in this world.

According to the Quran, the trust was presented to the sky, the earth, and the mountains, but they declined to accept it due to fear. Ultimately, it was assumed by mankind. Individuals have a propensity for cruelty and lack knowledge. Furthermore, the passage "" clearly demonstrates this reality.

Human Responsibility and Management in Islam

Encompass not just attitudes and actions directed towards God, but also those directed towards society and the environment. As stewards of the Earth, entrusted by God, people are bestowed with the responsibility and power to safeguard the welfare and protection of our planet. Individuals have the responsibility to engage in the worship of Allah, align their ideas, emotions, and actions with the intended purpose of creation, and lead a life of perfect submission to Allah. Muslims are obligated to not only fulfill their religious obligations to Allah, but also their obligations to society and the environment. These obligations include the need to be knowledgeable, behave with politeness, and safeguard the natural surroundings. Muslims are encouraged to recognize the

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interconnection between themselves and the natural world and to actively engage in efforts to conserve, maintain, and safeguard the environment for the benefit of future generations. Individuals possess obligations not alone to the divine entity, but also to the community and the natural world. Humans, as stewards of the world created by God, are responsible for supervising and administering it. They are obligated to advocate for sustainable practices and safeguard the environment. This entails seeing the environment as a sacred responsibility, refraining from squandering its resources, and being mindful of the repercussions of human acts within it. Islamic principles dictate that individuals must engage in the worship and obedience of Allah, seek knowledge, exhibit virtuous behavior, and properly rule the world. Society and Environment, Management, and Responsibility are represented by the acronym "SEMR." Humans have been entrusted with the responsibility of preserving and overseeing the Earth as custodians of God's creation. They have the duty to safeguard and conserve the environment via the promotion of sustainable practices. This entails seeing the environment as a sacred responsibility, refraining from squandering its resources, and being mindful of the repercussions of human acts within it. According to Islamic doctrine, individuals are accountable for their actions in the hereafter and have obligations towards both society and the environment. Within the framework of Islam, individuals have obligations not alone for their conduct towards other individuals, but also towards society and the natural surroundings. In accordance with Islamic doctrine, individuals are deemed accountable for their actions in the hereafter and are obligated to fulfill their duties towards both the community and the natural world. In Islam, people have responsibility not just for their own conduct, but also for their impact on society and the environment. In Islam, people are obligated to fulfill their duties not just towards Allah, but also towards society and the environment. Muslims are urged to engage in environmental stewardship and promote sustainable practices as part of their Islamic obligations. This view perceives the environment as a holy thing and a gift bestowed by a divine authority, necessitating reverence and safeguarding for current and future societies. In Islam, the link between people and the environment is founded on the belief that Allah is the creator of the environment and has entrusted mankind with the responsibility of safeguarding it. In

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accordance with Islamic tenets, individuals have the responsibility of safeguarding the environment and nourishing both living organisms and the natural ecosystem. In Islam, people have a duty to fulfill their obligations towards Allah, society, and the environment, and their involvement in protecting these entities is crucial. In Islam, people have responsibility not just towards Allah, but also towards society and their surroundings. In Islam, people are obligated to fulfill their duties not just towards Allah, but also towards society and the environment. On our planet, individuals are entrusted with the duty of exercising responsible leadership. In Islam, people are entrusted with the task of safeguarding and fostering the environment and all living beings. The concept of Tawhid, which refers to the oneness of Allah and the idea of guardianship, acknowledges that people in Islamic faith have responsibility for their conduct towards both society and the environment.

With regards to the topic at hand, it is evident that one of the fundamental responsibilities of an individual is to attentively heed and dutifully comply with the most excellent and wise utterances. "Deliver positive information to individuals who actively listen and adhere to the most excellent expressions!" The passage corroborates this. In order to properly perform the role of a servant, a person must possess a comprehensive awareness of their identity, purpose, and the factors that led to their being. There exists both a theoretical aspect of "listening" and a practical aspect of "compliance". During this stage of hearing, an individual acknowledges, comprehends, and situates himself. Self-awareness and self-understanding lead individuals to see their purpose in this world as serving God.

These passages unequivocally demonstrate that obedience, devotion, and prayer are crucial prerequisites for attaining worthiness in the eyes of Allah. According to the Holy Quran, a primary purpose for human being is to undergo a test. By adopting this approach, an individual may get a comprehensive understanding of their own existence, the external reality, the concept of the afterlife, and the phenomenon of death. He is the one responsible for both the creation of death and life, and he demonstrates superior conduct. He has great physical strength and has a generous and understanding nature. Allah states that upon sending man to this planet, He also designated him as

a caliph.

When God commanded the angels, saying, "I shall appoint a successor on the earth." "Will You appoint an individual who will engage in malicious activities and commit acts of violence, while we extol Your virtues and proclaim Your sanctity?" they inquired. "Truly, I possess knowledge that is unknown to you," Allah said. He was exclusively designated as the Caliph by Hz. It is the property of all mankind, not just Adam. Caliphate denotes the responsibilities of individuals to enforce and administer God's laws on earth. Allah communicates with mankind to enable them to exercise their own preferences while performing their responsibilities as Allah's representatives on Earth and carrying out their caliphate tasks effectively. It is evident that the human race, originating from Adam, is the most fitting entity for the caliphate. Regardless of whether one serves as a caliph for God or for other humans, individuals have the ability to fulfill this responsibility to the utmost extent due to their possession of free choice.

Human beings are the only entities capable of carrying out the duty of caring for the planet. Other entities lack this capability.

Hence, mankind is incapable of substituting for the divine being. Due to the constraints of available human resources. Nevertheless, each individual has an obligation and accountability in this realm. Whether it is the establishment of a caliphate or the acceptance of slavery, mankind has assumed this responsibility, and God has bestowed upon him the gift of knowledge.

DIMENSIONS OF HUMAN EXISTENCE

1- Physiological and Biological Dimension

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Humans possess both physiological and anatomical structures. Man was formed by God, with land and water as the fundamental constituents. A human being is first born as a sentient organism and may sustain its existence by consuming food that contains certain vitamins and minerals. The human body functions, matures, and expands via the assimilation of nutrients. H₂O is the predominant molecule, constituting around 55-60 percent of the human body.

The composition consists of around 5% inorganic molecules and 30-35% organic compounds. Approximately 98% of the human body is composed of bio-organic components. Various chemical and physical activities take place in the human body due to the presence of molecules, elements, and the fact that it is a living entity. These chemicals and components are present in humans and constitute the biological framework of the human body. The human body consists of several organs such as the eyes, ears, hands, feet, veins, and blood, all of which are determined by God's decision.

The Importance of Environmental Management in Islam

- In Islam, accountability refers to the individual's responsibility towards not just God, but also society and the environment. Muslims are recognizing that the environment has a holy status and is bestowed upon them as a divine blessing (Saleh and Hasan, 2019). Hence, it is incumbent upon them to proactively safeguard and conserve the environment for both present and future generations. Muslims are urged to embrace sustainable methods that see environmental conservation as a religious obligation. Islamic teachings have firmly established the notion of duty and care for the environment, highlighting the interconnectedness of all living beings and their need on a robust and harmonious ecosystem (Farhana et al., 2021). In Islam, the connection between people and the environment is founded on the belief that God is the creator of the environment and has bestowed upon mankind the responsibility of serving as custodians. Preserving the environment is a religious obligation for all individuals in Islam. It is imperative for

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Muslims to adopt proactive measures in order to save the environment, since they will be held responsible for their acts in the hereafter. In Islam, the notion of accountability encompasses more than just adherence to one's obligations towards God. According to Ousama and Fatima (2010), Muslims have obligations towards both society and the environment. In Islamic theology, the environment is seen as a divine gift. Hence, it is the duty of Muslims to responsibly govern the world and safeguard all forms of life. The notion of trust, known as tawakkul in Islam, plays a crucial role in shaping the interaction between individuals and their surroundings. Muslims have a moral duty to safeguard the world in order to ensure its long-term survival for future generations. The Islamic religion places great emphasis on responsibility and safeguarding, leading to a profound dedication to the preservation and safeguarding of the environment (El-Sherbini et al., 2023). Advocating for the conservation of natural resources and the reduction of waste by promoting sustainable practices such as recycling, energy conservation, and water conservation. - Ensuring the preservation of the rights of animals and plants and providing them with proper care - are a few instances of this dedication. • Mitigating pollution and minimizing environmental harm via practices such as conscientious waste disposal and the reduction of carbon emissions According to Islam, mankind has the duty of safeguarding the environment as caretakers appointed by God (Saleh and Hasan, 2019). This obligation includes the implementation of sustainable policies, the preservation of natural resources, and the equitable treatment of all living organisms. Islamic teachings dictate that mankind have been designated by God as custodians and, as such, it is their responsibility to safeguard and maintain the environment. In Islam, there exists a significant correlation between people and creation since humans are believed to be divinely entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment. Ultimately, Islam underscores the duty of humans as divinely appointed custodians to safeguard and conserve the environment. In Islam, people have the responsibility for both the welfare of society and the preservation of the environment. As stated by Ousama and Fatima (2010), this perspective originates from

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the belief that people have a responsibility to take care of all that God has created. According to Islam, people are considered conscientious leaders sent by God and are responsible for safeguarding and conserving the environment (Saleh and Hasan, 2019). In Islam, there exists a significant connection between people and their creations, rooted in the belief that human beings are divinely assigned the responsibility of safeguarding the environment. In Islam, people are seen as custodians of the environment established by Allah, thereby establishing an inherent connection between humans and the natural world. In Islam, the concept of human being and creation emphasizes that people are brought into being by Allah and are entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment. In Islam, there is a natural and inherent connection between man and his creation. As the custodian of the environment, humanity perceives it as a divine creation and a solemn responsibility. In Islam, there exists a significant connection between humanity and the act of creation. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, it is incumbent upon humanity to safeguard it. In Islam, there exists an inherent link between people and the natural world, since it is believed that humans have a duty to fulfill. This duty includes the obligation of nurturing and safeguarding the environment, which is seen to be a divine creation. The Islamic religion emphasizes the need of everyone to safeguard and conserve the environment that has been created by God. Islam posits an inherent connection between people and their surroundings, rooted on the belief that humans have been bestowed with the divine responsibility of scrutinizing the natural realm. Within the Islamic religion, there exists an inherent connection between people and nature, since it is believed that God has bestowed upon mankind the duty to appropriately steward the environment. In Islam, there exists a significant correlation between people and their creations, predicated on the notion that human beings are divinely tasked with safeguarding the environment. In Islamic doctrine, it is believed that God, in His role as the caretaker of the world, has entrusted mankind with the duty to safeguard and conserve the environment. According to Muslims, the responsibility of taking care of the

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natural world was given to mankind by God, establishing an inherent link between humans and the environment (Arlı et al., 2021). In Islam, there exists a significant connection between humanity and creation. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, people have a responsibility to safeguard it. In Islam, there exists an inherent connection between humanity and nature. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, it is incumbent upon humanity to safeguard it. There is an essential tie between humanity and creation in Islam. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, it is incumbent upon humanity to safeguard it. According to Islamic teachings, mankind has been entrusted with the responsibility to safeguard and conserve the environment, in addition to God's obligation to do so. The divine mandate to safeguard the environment established by God establishes an inherent bond in Islam between humanity and the natural world. In Islam, there exists a significant connection between humanity and the act of creation. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, it is incumbent upon humanity to safeguard it. According to Islamic beliefs, humans have the responsibility to safeguard and conserve the environment as caretakers of God's creation. In Islam, people are entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment, which establishes an inherent bond between humanity and creation. Islamic management ethics highlights the significance of people as integral components of a comprehensive living system established by God and underscores their duty to safeguard and conserve the environment (Gifford and Nilsson, 2014). According to Arlı et al. (2021), Muslims hold the belief that God has assigned mankind with the responsibility of taking care of the natural world, indicating a significant link between humans and the environment. In Islam, individuals have the responsibility of safeguarding the environment that has been created by God. Muslims prioritize environmental conservation due to their belief in the divine creation of the environment by Allah. In Islam, it is believed that God has entrusted human beings with

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the responsibility of safeguarding and fostering the environment. In accordance with Islamic teachings, mankind has been entrusted with the responsibility of becoming the custodian of the earth. They must acknowledge their duty to safeguard and defend the environment as an integral aspect of their religious beliefs. In Islamic theology, it is emphasized that God has designated humans as the caretakers of the planet and entrusted them with the task of safeguarding its welfare and preserving it as an integral component of his creation. In Islam, there exists a significant connection between humanity and the act of creation. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, it is incumbent upon humanity to safeguard it. In Islam, it is believed that human beings were created with the purpose of overseeing and safeguarding the environment, which is considered to be a divine entity. Nurturing and safeguarding it is a sacred duty. In Islamic theology, mankind is entrusted with the responsibility of serving as custodians of the environment, which is regarded as a sacred creation. In Islamic theology, it is believed that while the world is considered a sacred creation of God, it is the responsibility of human people to act as custodians of the environment. According to Islamic tenets, it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard God's creations. In Islam, there exists an inherent connection between humanity and nature. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, it is incumbent upon humanity to safeguard it. According to the Islamic religion, mankind is designated by God to be custodians of the environment and have the responsibility, as their own creations, to ensure the welfare of the environment. In Islam, the link between mankind and the natural world revolves upon the concept that humans have been entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment, which was created by God. In Islam, the concept of humanity being obligated to safeguard the environment due to its divine creation establishes a significant connection between humans and their surroundings. Islamic teachings mandate that mankind has been entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the environment, which is seen as a crucial aspect of their religious and

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ethical obligations. In Islam, there exists a significant connection between humanity and the act of creation. This relationship is predicated on the notion that since the environment was fashioned by a divine entity, it is incumbent upon humanity to safeguard it. According to Islamic teachings, Allah is regarded as the custodian of the world. They have the obligation to conserve and safeguard the environment since it is an integral aspect of their religious beliefs. In accordance with Islamic tenets, it is incumbent upon mankind to safeguard the environment fashioned by the divine and guarantee its welfare. In accordance with Islamic teachings, mankind is entrusted with the task of safeguarding the environment, assuming the responsibility of promoting its welfare and preserving it as a divine creation. Islam underscores individuals' need to save and conserve the environment as a significant aspect of their faith and responsibilities. They were designated by God to serve as custodians of the planet. on Islam, there exists an inherent connection between people and the natural world, rooted on the belief that God has designated mankind as stewards of the natural realm. In order to secure the long-term well-being and sustainability of the environment for future generations, it is imperative that Muslims take proactive measures to conserve and preserve it. In Islam, the concept of the link between mankind and the natural world revolves upon the notion that humans have been entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment, which has been brought into existence by God. Therefore, it is imperative for Muslims to take proactive measures to safeguard and conserve the environment, ensuring its welfare for future generations and maintaining its long-term viability. Islam's link between mankind and the natural world is founded on the notion that they must care for the environment established by God. Consequently, it is imperative for Muslims to take proactive measures to save and preserve the environment. This guarantees the continued success and durability of the entity for future generations. In Islam, people have an inseparable connection with creatures since they are entrusted by God with the responsibility of being stewards of the world. Thus, as custodians of God's creation, Muslims have a duty to safeguard and enhance the environment, both now and for

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the benefit of future generations. The relationship between mankind and the environment is inherently intertwined, since Islam mandates that humans have a responsibility to protect and preserve the natural world, which is considered a divine creation (Arli et al., 2021). Ultimately, it is incumbent for Muslims to maintain and defend the environment, diligently assuming the role of conscientious custodians, and faithfully fulfilling and safeguarding their Islamic obligations.

As individuals are physical entities, some connections and interdependencies emerge from the surrounding environment in which they reside. These partnerships are vital for the continuation of life. The extent of human reliance on the material realm may be comprehended via the utilization of water, oxygen, protein, and sustenance. Nevertheless, man has both spiritual and metaphysical aspects. Another sign of metaphysical dedication is the desire to transcend by engaging in interpersonal connections and engaging in thoughtful and logical thinking. Various variables contribute to individuals' will to persevere in life. The soul, in addition to the physiological and biochemical makeup of a human being, is an entity that allows for the essence of humanity to manifest. Nevertheless, the soul remains timeless, unchanging, and unaffected by aging, renewal, or fluctuations in size. Consequently, the soul lacks the attributes seen in the physical human body. The essence of an individual's soul stays constant throughout their whole lifespan, from the moment of birth to the moment of death. Nevertheless, death encompasses more than only the physical deterioration of the body or the spiritual departure of the soul. The cause might be attributed to biological obsolescence or faults in the body. The electrochemical capability of the human body diminishes with age. The behavior of water molecules diminishes in an indeterminate manner. An individual's organs experience a decline in youthful vitality, resulting in diminished functionality and overall physical inadequacy. The human body lacks the capacity to regenerate a significant quantity of essential cells, leading to mortality.

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The human body is composed of living cells. The cellular architecture undergoes continuous regeneration inside the human body. Renewal of cells occurs when old cells in the body are replaced with new ones. Thus, from a biological perspective, death does not transpire abruptly, but rather unfolds gradually. Extensive scientific inquiry and discourse have explored the need of corporeal death. Ongoing research is being conducted on this topic. Nevertheless, a definitive resolution has not been reached. Death signifies the cessation of physiological processes and is the ultimate outcome predetermined by Allah. This is an unavoidable conclusion that every organism on earth will inevitably encounter. According to the Quran, "Every living being experiences death." Afterwards, you shall be returned to us." The poem substantiates this truth.

2- Spiritual Dimension

The soul is recognized as one of the constituent parts of an individual. Islamic scholars concur that the human person is comprised of both a physical body and an immaterial spirit, as shown by their definitions. Nevertheless, intellectuals have always engaged in discussions over the essence of the soul. The soul is one of the constituent elements of a human person. The soul is an independent topic of investigation. The term "soul" is used in twenty-one instances throughout the Holy Quran. The word "spirit" refers to the element that imbues living things with life and facilitates their movement. The soul is believed to be linked with the body via five distinct modalities. 1. During intrauterine development. 2. Following successful birth. 3. Fatigue. 4. It is situated in Barzakh. 5. Apocalypse

Death is the event that occurs when the human spirit departs from the physical body. The soul has significance in this context. The term "soul" is used to refer to the spiritual essence of a human being, which is believed to be taken by angels under the authority of Allah. The human soul is immaterial and distinct from the physical body. The soul unequivocally acknowledges the

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existence of God inside mankind, serving as the embodiment and authority of man's spiritual dimension. The soul bestows to the human person the faculties of awareness, cognition, perception, and volition. The spiritual dimension is imperceptible to the senses. Throughout a person's lifespan, their physical structure undergoes continuous development. However, self-awareness indicates that a human is distinct from their physical existence, and the fundamental entity responsible for this self-awareness is the soul. Despite the biological decline and aging of the human body, the essence of life persists until death.

Furthermore, the human mind bestows to individuals the capacity to engage in cognitive processes such as thinking, comprehending, and perceiving. The mind is a crucial attribute that sets humans apart from other entities. Every scientific discipline has provided its own distinct definition of the mind.

In the Holy Quran, the mind is described as a faculty that has the ability to acquire knowledge and is responsible for the acquisition of information. The capacity of reason guarantees that humans possess accountability and are held responsible for adhering to divine laws and restrictions. This imbues significance to their actions. The human mind apprehends concepts of goodness, truth, and beauty, engages in cognitive processes, and scrutinizes its own conduct. He comprehends once again, intellectually, that the purpose of his being in this world is to confront the challenges of life. He has the ability to effectively handle any challenge or obstacle by using astute strategies. He maintains equilibrium between his own emotions, desires, and melancholy and his rational thinking. Reason is what distinguishes humans from other beings. In Islamic theology, the mind is seen as a profound gift, second only to faith. It has immense value since it serves as a means to achieve the hereafter.

Willpower is the cognitive capacity to make a deliberate choice about the execution or avoidance of a certain action. Willingness may be described as the desire or willingness to accomplish a task or reach a certain goal. The topic of volition has been extensively debated throughout Islamic

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history. Indeed, there have been the emergence of sects such as Cehmiyye, which asserts that human beings lack freedom in their activities, and Kaderiye, which asserts that human beings possess absolute freedom. According to the Holy Quran, the divine will is completely unrestricted and has inherent wisdom, ensuring that Allah is fair.

Nevertheless, the test's objective necessitates granting individuals the freedom to use their own will in making decisions. While the Holy Quran acknowledges the ultimate will of Allah, it also affirms that people possess the autonomy to exercise their own moral agency and make independent decisions. "We will obtain worldly benefits from anyone who desires them." We provide the prize of the afterlife to all those who request it. "We have indeed guided him to the correct course; now it is up to him whether he will show gratitude or ingratitude." Nevertheless, the Holy Quran provides guidance to individuals based on their activities and emphasizes that seeking God's approval will provide advantages for them. Exercise your freedom of choice but be aware that Allah is observing your actions. Individuals are liberated upon successfully completing the examination, although all their actions in the earthly realm will be fulfilled in the realm beyond.

3- Psychological Dimension

Psychology primarily examines the origins and determinants of human behavior. The Holy Quran elucidates human behavior and provides insights into the underlying factors influencing it. When discussing man, he asserts that man has an inherent character, which serves as the primary determinant of his conduct, and that man is predisposed to hold certain beliefs. Devote yourself entirely to religion as a hanif and direct your attention towards the natural world that Allah has used to shape humanity! God's creations are immutable. This is the authentic faith; however it remains largely unrecognized by the majority of people. The Quran embodies several aspects of human nature, including weakness, selfishness, jealousy, ingratitude, impatience, and lack of

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gratitude. This suggests the presence of characteristics like as

Individuals want to lead their lives in accordance with their own preferences and inclinations. According to the Holy Quran, individuals may achieve inner peace and exert control over their negative habits, regardless of their conduct. If we bestow a blessing onto an individual and then revoke it, that individual will be left utterly devoid of hope and gratitude. "According to him, bestowing a blessing upon him following a difficult experience will result in the cessation of unfavorable circumstances for me," he states.

Currently, his only activities consist of experiencing happiness and boasting. However, this does not apply to those who demonstrate patience and engage in virtuous actions for both the present life and the hereafter. They see this as a philanthropic contribution and a significant accolade. Emotions have a crucial role in shaping human behavior. Emotion has the ability to have profound effects on an individual. Heightened emotional states might lead individuals to develop a compelling inclination towards certain behaviors. Emotion is the subjective perception and response that an individual feels and elicits inside their inner realm in relation to certain things, events, or others. The distinctive capacity for emotional experience is the defining characteristic of human spiritual mobility. It is a psychological phenomenon characterized by the occurrence of unconscious experiences in an individual as a result of internal or external factors. Human emotions are varied and intricate due to their complicated nature. Human emotions include a range of feelings such as love, sorrow, anger, resentment, grief, worry, fear, and others. The individuality of these emotions among different individuals adds a distinctive aspect to this subject. Individuals' emotional experiences vary, as emotions may differ across genders (men and women), age groups (young and old), and between children and adults. Emotions are constantly influenced by an individual's surroundings, ingenuity, personal growth, and lived encounters. Emotional experiences exhibit individual variation. Due to the distinct nature of their scopes, categorizing human emotions, assessing them separately, and creating a comprehensive categorization akin to a mathematical formula is incredibly challenging.

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BASIC HUMAN EMOTIONS

1- Sense of Faith

Physical and biological actions, such as eating, drinking, and breathing, are also influenced by spiritual activities, such as believing, celebrating, and experiencing happiness. What sets man apart from other creatures is the infusion of God's soul into him. Consequently, he has a human nature that encompasses both his bodily and spiritual aspects. Belief in an entity is a fundamental aspect of human cognition and cognitive processes. Human nature is inherently determined. Virtually every individual on the planet has the inherent need to have faith and find refuge. The experience of faith elicits a transformation in an individual's conduct and engenders a range of emotional states. The belief in the presence of God serves as a significant and influential driving force in the life of a devout individual. A one who has faith understands that they are not solitary in the realm. He perceives the existence of a sentient being that is aware of him, observes him, is intimately connected to him, and provides assistance at challenging moments. This intense emotion causes a believer to experience despair while also maintaining a continual state of vitality and alertness. An individual who has a keen sense of faith experiences a state of mental and spiritual equilibrium and well-being as a result of their unwavering confidence in a higher power, namely God. With a submissive mindset, he remains steadfast even in the most challenging circumstances, recognizing that they are all part of God's plan and a means of testing his faith. Consequently, he does not succumb to despair or anxiety.

2- Feeling of Love

Love is an innate feeling inherent in human nature from the beginning of existence. The love of

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Allah is unquestionably the utmost superior and invaluable. Muslims should see Allah as the paramount entity in their life and prioritize their devotion to Him above everything else. "Certain individuals regard certain entities as deities on par with Allah, and they hold an affection for these entities that is comparable to their love for Allah." Those who have the greatest devotion to Allah are the ones who believe in Him the most. "Seek absolution from your Lord and subsequently engage in sincere repentance." "Truly, my Lord," he said, "His love and mercy are plentiful." He is the only possessor of boundless love, the rightful ruler of the kingdom, the epitome of splendor, and has the freedom to act as he pleases. He alone possesses the power to forgive abundantly. He is the rightful ruler of the throne, the one who holds authority and dominion. He is the embodiment of glory and possesses the freedom to act as he pleases. The passages of God's love are boundless. You have the potential to receive divine love from God due to your profound devotion to Him. Merely experiencing affection does not seem sufficient to get this love and validation. Hence, it is imperative to translate this affection into actions and conduct oneself in accordance with divine instructions. Individuals who engage in virtuous actions with the intention of securing a positive afterlife outcome are exempt from guilt, provided they refrain from committing transgressions, uphold their religious beliefs, persist in doing good acts, maintain their abstinence, adhere to their faith, avoid sinful behavior, and strive to achieve excellence, regardless of their past use of food and drink. Those who comply with Allah's approval have affection for Him. The devout individuals generously contribute to the cause of Allah, regardless of their circumstances, by controlling their wrath and displaying forgiveness towards others. Allah favors those who do their tasks with excellence. Just as there are individuals whom Allah holds dear, there are also those whom He does not like. Nonbelievers approach those whom they have animosity against. To clarify, Allah disapproves of those who engage in both polytheism and immoral actions. This signifies his aversion towards individuals who engage in malevolent actions, exhibit extreme behavior, surpass boundaries, display ingratitude, commit sins, demonstrate arrogance, boast, and exhibit pride, act cruelly, perpetrate injustice, and fail to uphold their commitments (including acts of treason and wastefulness). Individuals who lack affection for God or fail to demonstrate devotion towards God

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are characterized by their inability to adhere to God's desired behavior, their limited capacity to establish profound connections with God, and their inclination to prioritize affection for other creatures above God. The prevalence of earthly affections hinders individuals from cultivating love for God and diminishes their affection for Him.

Humans naturally experience affection for a variety of entities. Allah admonishes individuals for their attachment to possessions, as if they have the same level of affection for Allah. An individual's predisposition towards worldly matters and attachment to material riches might lead to the neglect of their devotion to Allah. Individuals have a strong affinity for the merchandise. That is the reason why individuals have a strong like for products. The Holy Quran explicitly highlights the tendency of individuals to develop a strong dependency on material possessions. "His avid pursuit of wealth had a profound influence on him."

3- Feeling of Fear

Individuals experience interior fear. Individuals respond to stimuli that pose a threat or have the potential to cause damage. Individuals often experience fear in response to novel and unfamiliar entities.

Individuals vary in their degree of apprehension and the objects of their apprehension. Universal terror is a conceivable feeling for all individuals. An individual has distinct anxieties throughout their youth, maturity, and old life. Fear is the emotional response to an undesirable event or circumstance. When an unfavorable event occurs, an individual experiences emotional distress, characterized by heartache, burning sensations, and profound sadness. This anxiety elicits discomfort in individuals. The Quran inquires, "Have you been informed of the narrative of the complainants?" Through his inquiry, he elucidates the innate apprehension present in individuals. David scaled the wall of the temple and gained in. David was astounded at seeing their presence.

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"Fear not," they said, "we are two litigants, one of whom accuses the other of committing an act of injustice." Please make a sincere choice between us; refrain from straying from the incorrect course and guide us towards the correct route. dread is characterized by the tendency of an individual to flee from the stimulus or entity that elicits dread. The dread of God is distinct from any other fear experienced towards anything or anybody in the world. The fear of God is an inherent aspect of man's connection with the divine. Numerous literary works have explored the theme of "astonishment and optimism". The apprehension in this context does not pertain to God himself, but rather to the consequences that may result from his actions. When confronted with terror, individuals may be able to avoid or evade the source of their fear in the physical world, but they cannot elude or evade the presence and might of Allah. It is impossible to evade or elude God. Hakim Abu-l Kasim said, "One who experiences fear towards something tends to avoid that particular thing." Individuals who have apprehension towards God seek refuge in God. Nevertheless, those who seek shelter in Allah are liberated from the apprehension of Allah.

Management Ethics in Islam: Protecting and Protecting the Environment as Stewards of God's Creation

In Islam, the concept of the link between mankind and the natural world revolves upon the notion that humans have been entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment, which is a creation of God. In order to guarantee the sustainability and well-being of future generations, it is imperative for Muslims to actively safeguard and preserve the environment. The notion of Amanah embodies the divine trust and duty bestowed upon humans by God. Devout Muslims who safeguard the sanctity of God's creation acknowledge their accountability for their deeds on the Day of Judgment. Muslims get guidance from the Quran and Sunnah in their endeavors to save the environment. They adhere to the principle of waste reduction and equilibrium. Regrettably, I am unable to provide a response given the available resources. In Islam, the concept of the link between

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mankind and the natural world revolves upon the notion that humans have been entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment, which was created by God. Hence, it is imperative for Muslims to diligently carry out their religious obligations, serve as vigilant custodians, and safeguard the environment's welfare and longevity for the sake of future progeny. Management in Islam encompasses more than only the preservation and conservation of the environment. Muslims are urged to enhance and advance their surroundings in alignment with the equilibrium set by Allah. This truth is shown by the teachings of Islam and the conduct of early Muslim leaders. For instance, the first Caliph Abu Bakr granted permission to down fruit trees, incinerate dwellings or wheat fields, or annihilate palm palms, unless there was a need to do so (Arli and Tjiptono, 2017). By upholding the principles of Islam and adopting the concept of governance, Muslims not only fulfill their religious obligations but also enhance the general welfare of the globe and its inhabitants (Gifford and Nilsson, 2014). In Islam, people are seen as an integral component of everything that has been created by Allah, and they are entrusted with the responsibility of carefully overseeing the world. The objective of this mission is to safeguard the ecosystem, promote healthy diet, and preserve the environment. It is incumbent upon Muslims to safeguard and uphold the world that has been brought into existence by the divine. This concept acknowledges the planet as a sacred gift and assigns humanity the responsibility of conserving and safeguarding the ecosystem. In accordance with Islamic teachings, individuals safeguard the environment due to their belief in its divine creation. Therefore, it is imperative for Muslims to conscientiously execute their obligation as caregivers to ensure the fulfillment of their religious duties and secure the well-being and sustainability of future generations. Gifford and Nilsson (2014) highlight that Islam places significant emphasis on humanity's need to effectively oversee and safeguard the environment. According to Islam, people have been entrusted by God with the responsibility to safeguard, defend, and foster the environment (Mostafa, 2016). Islam emphasizes the responsibility of humanity to actively safeguard, conserve, and foster the environment as a sacred duty. Islam underscores the notion that people have been designated by God as custodians of the environment and are so accountable for its conservation, safeguarding, and cultivation. Islam underscores the

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significance of mankind as caretakers and the role of communication in safeguarding the environment for Muslims.

Islam places great emphasis on communication, particularly in regard to safeguarding the environment. Islam acknowledges the significance of communication in advancing environmental conservation efforts and fostering consciousness. Muslims are urged to engage actively in environmental dialogues as it fosters heightened consciousness and accountability towards safeguarding the environment. Through the dissemination of knowledge and the promotion of open dialogue, Muslims may collaborate to safeguard the preservation of God's creation and discover viable resolutions. Muslims has the capacity to educate individuals on the significance of safeguarding the environment, foster a collective sense of accountability, and promote the adoption of sustainable habits. They may do this by using clear and efficient communication. In Islam, the concept of the link between mankind and the natural world revolves upon the notion that humans have been entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment, which has been brought into existence by God. Hence, it is imperative for Muslims to diligently carry out their religious obligations, actively safeguard and conserve the environment, assume the role of responsible caretakers, and secure the welfare and sustainability of future generations. Ultimately, Islam asserts that it is the responsibility of mankind, as ordained by God, to actively safeguard, conserve, and foster the environment. Ultimately, Islam maintains the belief that it is the responsibility of mankind, as ordained by God, to actively safeguard, conserve, and foster the environment. Within the Islamic faith, individuals have a moral duty to safeguard the environment as a sacred responsibility and are required to actively conserve, shield, and cultivate it. According to Islamic beliefs, it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard, conserve, and foster the environment as it is given by God. In accordance with Islamic teachings, individuals have a religious duty to safeguard, protect, and foster the environment as a sacred responsibility. In the Islamic faith, people are considered custodians of the environment and are responsible for actively safeguarding, defending, and fostering it as a divine gift. Islam asserts that people are divinely

designated as custodians of the environment, with the duty to safeguard, protect, and foster it. Islam asserts that mankind has been entrusted by God with the responsibility of becoming stewards of the environment, necessitating their active engagement in the conservation, safeguarding, and fostering of the natural world. Ultimately, the Islamic faith underscores the responsibility bestowed upon humanity by God to actively safeguard, conserve, and foster the environment.

The Importance of Environmental Management in Islam

In Islam, the need to safeguard the environment, established by Allah, governs the connection between humans and their surroundings. Muslims have a duty to actively safeguard, defend, and foster the environment as guardians sent by God. This duty entails protecting the welfare and enduring viability of the environment and conserving it for future generations. Another crucial aspect of Islam is the belief that people will be held accountable for the environmental damage they do in the hereafter. In addition, Islam acknowledges the significance of promoting environmental consciousness and fostering collaborative endeavors pertaining to the environment. Consequently, Islam maintains that mankind has been assigned by God with the responsibility to safeguard and foster the environment, ensuring its preservation and nourishment. According to Islamic teachings, individuals are obligated to safeguard the environment since they are divinely assigned to actively ensure the protection, conservation, and enhancement of the natural world. Islam places significant emphasis on the crucial responsibility of individuals to save the environment. The notion highlights the moral and ethical duty of humans to safeguard and rehabilitate the environment, while simultaneously minimizing their ecological footprint via localized and community-oriented initiatives. They have a duty to actively safeguard, conserve, and cultivate the environment as a component of their designated purpose. According to Islamic teachings, it is the responsibility of mankind to maintain, safeguard, and enhance the environment as bestowed by God. Ultimately, Islam asserts that people have been granted authority by God to function as guardians of the

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environment, necessitating their active involvement in the conservation, safeguarding, and cultivation of the natural world. Ultimately, Islam underscores the notion that it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment, as bestowed upon them by God. Islam asserts that mankind has been entrusted by God with the duty to safeguard, protect, and foster the environment. Islam asserts that mankind has been entrusted by God with the responsibility of being stewards of the environment, necessitating their need to safeguard, conserve, and foster it. Consequently, the Islamic faith empowers individuals to assume the duty of safeguarding, shielding, and fostering their surroundings as custodians sent by God.

The Role of Man as Environmental Responsible in Islam

Islam underscores the significant responsibility individuals have in safeguarding the environment. According to Islamic teachings, it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment as bestowed by God. It is stressed that this duty is a crucial component of the entire system of existence established by God. Thus, mankind has been entrusted with the duty to rule the earth diligently. Managers have an ethical and moral obligation to protect and restore the environment. This helps to minimize humanity's negative influence on nature by promoting development that is focused on local communities. In Islam, people are seen as stewards of the world. They are obligated to safeguard it against any kind of degradation. Moreover, Islam regards the environment as a divine blessing (Saleh and Hasan, 2019). Consequently, Muslims are obligated to safeguard the environment and maintain the equilibrium established by Allah by their actions (Mostafa, 2016). Islam also underscores the need of environmental communication. Muslims are urged to actively endeavor to resolve environmental issues. Islam asserts that it is the responsibility of humanity, as ordained by God, to actively safeguard, conserve, and foster the environment. According to Islamic beliefs, individuals are seen as custodians of the environment and have a moral duty to actively safeguard, conserve, and foster it as a sacred responsibility.

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According to Islamic teachings, individuals have a religious duty to safeguard the environment as a sacred responsibility and are required to actively conserve, shield, and foster it. In accordance with Islamic teachings, individuals have a religious duty to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment as a sacred responsibility. Consequently, the Islamic doctrine entails that individuals have the duty to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment. They have the ability to actively safeguard the environment as bestowed to them by a divine entity. In the Islamic religion, people are seen as custodians of the world, and as such, safeguarding and conserving the environment is considered a crucial ethical obligation. Precise weather predictions are crucial in the modern day. Thus, according to Islamic doctrine, it is the duty of humanity to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment. They have the ability to actively safeguard the environment, bestowed to them by God. In the Islamic religion, people are seen as custodians of the world, and as such, the preservation and safeguarding of the environment is considered a vital ethical obligation. Precise weather predictions are crucial in the contemporary day. According to Islamic teachings, individuals are obligated to safeguard, defend, and foster the environment, and they have the ability to actively safeguard it since it is a gift from God. According to Islamic teachings, individuals are obligated to safeguard, maintain, and foster the environment as a divine gift. This responsibility entails safeguarding the environment from deterioration and actively striving to enhance its long-term viability. Thus, according to Islamic doctrine, mankind is obligated to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment. They have the ability to actively safeguard the environment, bestowed to them by God. In accordance with Islamic tenets, individuals have the duty to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment.

An individual experiences fear in relation to a flood due to its potential to completely displace or destroy all possessions and belongings. Individuals harbor fear towards fire due to its inherent quality of combustion. Those who acquire knowledge of Allah's qualities experience fear, as they understand that if He were to annihilate the entire world, there would be no power capable of preventing it. An individual acknowledges that divine retribution may befall them as a consequence

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of their transgressions, since they have personal accountability for their own deeds. Consequently, it is natural for someone to have apprehension towards Allah if his actions are morally wrong. The reverence for Allah, in contrast to mundane apprehensions, serves as a catalyst for virtuous actions and fosters equilibrium. His Holiness, the Prophet, said, "I am the individual who harbors the greatest reverence for Allah among all of you." Upon acquiring knowledge of Allah, an individual develops both affection and apprehension towards Him. Acquiring knowledge may immerse an individual in both melancholy and sorrow. The dread of hunger in individuals instills a subsequent fear of poverty, as shown in the Quranic verse: "Only the erudite among His devotees harbor apprehension towards Allah." Individuals exert effort and may overcome challenges in order to sustain themselves and their families. This is an innate emotion experienced by the person.

He actively avoids and dreads any danger that hinders the growth of his resources, and experiences sadness when his resources diminish, or he confronts such a peril. Occasionally, one may have concerns about nourishment. His apprehensions may be the reason for his lack of desire to have children.

The genuine dread of a believer should be the fear of Allah. Because loving Allah and entirely submitting to Him removes all types of anxieties and brings people tranquility. As a consequence, believers should only dread the wrath and rage of Allah and should constantly live in the middle of fear and hope .

Fear of dying is one of people's biggest fears. Part of this world is human.

He continually works to preserve and maintain balance, order and harmony between himself and the world.

This order and balance of a person may be upset from time to time and not everyone's order may be at the same level. That's why people worry. The situations a person is in translate this worry into dread. Man's greatest dread is the fear of death and extinction. Faith in God alleviates a person's

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dread of death. Believers know that they will be rewarded with Allah's favor and kindness owing to their good works and deeds in this world, and that death is forever. Therefore, a believer is not scared of death, since he lives in line with God's plan and knows that he will be rewarded in the finest manner. Death has always been the dread of man, and man has always attempted to discover a means to get rid of death. Regarding death, most individuals do not desire death and do not seek a solution. However, it is mentioned in the Quran, "Every living thing will taste death."

4- Sociological Dimension

The social element has significance alongside the emotional, biological, and psychological aspects of human beings. Aside from his introspective connection with himself and his spiritual bond with God, man also maintains interpersonal relationships with others. Sociological relationships pertain to the interpersonal connections that an individual maintains with one or more individuals. This is contingent upon an individual's inherent disposition and is essential for their sustenance and maintenance of a sound well-being. The study of these interactions falls under the field of sociology. The social network of interpersonal connections spanning from birth to death is very varied.

Furthermore, death engenders certain social connections to develop inside an individual's existence. While all sciences may touch upon aspects of mortality, sociology specifically focuses on the study of social dynamics. Death is a sociological phenomenon with societal implications. Hence, mortality impacts social connections and alters their dynamics. Both the dead and other individuals see death as a communal occasion. Death refers to the cessation of biological, psychological, and other essential functions of a person. Furthermore, it also terminates its societal roles. Upon an individual's demise, a profound shift and metamorphosis take place within the realm of social interactions. During this process, the individuals inside the deceased's social network also

undergo changes and transformations, leading to a sense of loss and deprivation among them. The deceased's act of depriving has resulted in the development of specific funeral ceremonies that vary according on the deceased's rank, age, occupation, and position. Consequently, death became into a cultural phenomenon. These rituals serve a crucial role in alleviating the deprivation and sadness felt by the bereaved, allowing them to restore equilibrium in their life and reintegrate into society.

PERSON'S SITUATION FACED BY DEATH

1- Emotions and Attitudes Regarding Death

Mortality is the ultimate cessation that every individual will inevitably confront. Mortality is a topic that occupies the thoughts of every civilization and is imbued with significance. Even those who do not belong to any one group have interpreted and incorporated the concept of death into their religious practices, rituals, folklore, and myths. Nevertheless, every person has a unique perception of death. For some people, death elicits anxiety and tension, whereas for others, it brings them feelings of love and respite from stress. Thoughts of death may also be influenced by an individual's lifestyle, environment, family, and other related variables. Individuals lead diverse lifestyles based on their views, opinions, ideals, morals, and spiritual frameworks. Each individual has a unique response to the concept of mortality. The perception of death is influenced by its inevitability.

The perception of death in the sociocultural milieu is highly influenced by religious, medical, and ideological elements. An individual's perspective on death is shaped by their interpretation of life and existence, ultimately influencing their attitude towards mortality. Simultaneously, death influences an individual's outlook on life and the state of being. Comprehending attitudes towards death necessitates recognizing the significance of the bond between these two individuals.

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2. Death Anxiety and Fear: Fear is a fundamental emotion experienced by humans. This sensation is prevalent, and its origin remains unclear. Fear has substance, but anxiety lacks substance; The exact explanation is not entirely understood. Defining this illness is challenging due to the distinct but interrelated nature of anxiety and dread. The notions of fear and anxiety have long been conflated. Nearly every individual has a fear of mortality. The dread of death is distinct from other phobias due to its universal, profound, and awe-inspiring nature. The fear of mortality might stem from several underlying causes.

Ibn Sina lists the reasons for the fear of death as follows.

1-Not knowing the truth of death.

2-The inability to predict what will happen to a person after death.

3-To think that after the body decays and disappears, the personality and self will completely disappear, and that the existence of the universe will continue after it.

4-To think that there is also suffering for death, in addition to the pain and suffering of diseases that occur during life or lead to death.

5-Believing that there will be punishment and torture after death.

6- Being confused and not knowing where you will go and what will happen to you after you die.

7- Feeling sad about the property and inheritance he will leave behind.

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Imam Ghazali summarizes the reasons for the fear of death as follows.

1. A person is afraid of death because he will be deprived of the pleasures of life, 2. Because he will lose the goods and property he has in this world, 3. Because he does not know exactly whether his place after death will be good or bad.

2. Not knowing the exact truth of death, that is, uncertainty, causes people to experience anxiety and stress.

Since death cannot be observed fully, people worry about death. However, this anxiety and fear is expected to decrease when people fulfill the beliefs and worship prescribed by religion.

3. Desire to Be Immortal: A person does not want to die or perish. As mentioned above, death causes him anxiety and anxiety. There is a desire for immortality and survival in human nature.

The human need for eternal life is boundless. The aspiration of a finite and mortal individual in the presence of the divine is to attain immortality and transcend mortality. In order to achieve this aspiration, individuals devise novel concepts and ideologies pertaining to eternal life. Through the advancement of science and technology, individuals have used several scientific approaches in the pursuit of immortality. Cold therapy technology, or cryonics, is an overly ambitious approach. The objective of this approach is to promote the cryopreservation of deceased individuals for potential technological revival in the future, as opposed to traditional burial or cremation methods. Some individuals have formed official organizations in their respective nations to fulfill this objective. R. Ettinger, the originator of cryonics, provides the following explanation for the concept of cryopreserving individuals. Following our demise, it is advisable to preserve our remains in refrigeration units for the maximum duration that scientific advancements can support. The specific reason of death, whether it be attributed to old age or a severe illness, is inconsequential. At the

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right time, our acquaintances in the future will eventually find a remedy for our ailment and ensure our survival. The freezing procedure involves gradually lowering the body's temperature over a period of two days to -79°C , which is equivalent to the temperature of dry ice. Subsequently, his body is administered with prophylactic drugs. Subsequently, the body is encased in a woolen garment that retains its suppleness even at a frigid temperature of -196°C . Subsequently, the suit is immersed in a container filled with liquid nitrogen. At a temperature of -196°C , which is the boiling point of nitrogen, all biological functions come to a halt and the only remaining course of action is to wait. Biologists have the belief that this occurrence is unlikely to transpire. As to their statement, kidneys intended for transplantation may be preserved under ice for up to 48 hours, but hearts and livers may have a shorter preservation time. If you are unable to safeguard any of these organs for a duration beyond 48 hours, how will you ensure the protection of the whole body? These endeavors demonstrate that people possess a profound desire for immortality. The strength and magnitude of this desire differ across individuals. It might arise directly from the concept of immortality, as well as indirectly. The act of producing offspring and creating diverse works of art as a means to ensure the continuation of one's lineage and name may be seen as an indirect manifestation of the human need for immortality.

Islamic Environmental Ethics: Man and His Creation According to Islam

In accordance with Islamic teachings, it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment, and to aggressively defend it as it was bestowed to them by God. This desire arises from seeing the cosmos, including the surroundings, as a divine gift. In Islam, people are seen as an integral component of God's whole creation. They must embrace the role of becoming the most efficient leaders in the world, acknowledging that every living being, and ecological system have the natural entitlement to prosper and grow. Hence, individuals must assume the role of stewards and safeguard the environment while refraining from causing any

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disturbances. In addition, environmental communication has great significance in Islam since it is rooted in the communication capabilities bestowed upon mankind by Allah (Saleh and Hasan, 2019). Hence, it is important for Muslims to engage in effective communication within their own communities and acquire knowledge pertaining to environmental concerns. According to Islamic teachings, individuals are obligated to safeguard the environment and care for it as it is bestowed by God (Mostafa, 2016). Islam asserts that mankind has been entrusted with the responsibility of being stewards of the environment and are obligated to actively safeguard and preserve it. Thus, in accordance with Islamic tenets, individuals have a duty to safeguard, shield, and foster the environment as bestowed upon them by God. Within the Islamic faith, individuals have the duty to safeguard, defend, and foster the environment, seeing it as a divine gift. Within the Islamic faith, individuals have the duty of safeguarding, conserving, and fostering the environment, seeing it as a divine gift from God. According to Islamic teachings, individuals are obligated to actively safeguard, conserve, and foster the environment, seeing it as a divine gift. Islam asserts that mankind has the obligation of safeguarding and conserving the environment. According to Islamic teachings, mankind is obligated to safeguard the environment and preserve and nurture it in the manner bestowed to them by God. Within the Islamic faith, individuals have the duty to safeguard, protect, and foster the environment, seeing it as a divine gift. According to Islamic beliefs, humanity have been entrusted by God with the responsibility of becoming the custodians of the planet. This entails safeguarding and fostering it in accordance with the equilibrium ordained by God. Humans have a responsibility to oversee and safeguard the earth, in alignment with the maintenance of God's equilibrium. In Islam, the notion of mankind and their creation is rooted in the conviction that God has entrusted humankind with the responsibility of safeguarding the planet. This encompasses the duty to safeguard and nurture the planet, while also ensuring its alignment with the intended equilibrium set by God.

Islamic Perspective on Man and His Creation as the Protector of the Environment

From the Islamic standpoint, it is incumbent upon mankind to safeguard the environment as bestowed by God. Viewing the earth as a divine creation bestowed upon humanity, individuals assume the duty of safeguarding, shielding, and fostering the planet as caretakers. Individuals must refrain from engaging in activities that pose a threat to the environment, such as the destruction of forests, improper disposal of waste, and the release of pollutants. In addition, Islam promotes the spread of information and the cultivation of consciousness about environmental matters within the Muslim community, acknowledging the significance of communication in this context. It is imperative for Muslims to safeguard the environment and fulfill their role as caretakers. In the realm after death, individuals will face responsibility for all their actions. In Islam, people are seen as divine emissaries entrusted with the responsibility of supervising and safeguarding every facet of life, collaborating harmoniously with all of God's creations. According to Islamic beliefs, people are seen as divine emissaries entrusted with the responsibility of preserving the Earth (Ghazali et al., 2018). Environmental conservation has significant importance within religious doctrines. This obligation is contingent upon the idea of sustainability. From this standpoint, it is emphasized that people must safeguard and nurture the land, ensuring the welfare and prosperity of all living beings and ecosystems, while also preserving the equilibrium ordained by God. Therefore, according to Islam, it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard and foster the environment as mandated by God. Their objective is to promote the cultivation of the land in accordance with the whole of God's creation. The notion of governance in Islam necessitates individuals to assume the role of a conscientious leader in controlling the world (Gifford and Nilsson, 2014). Guardianship in Islam refers to the profound connection between people and things. In Islam, the responsibility of safeguarding and preserving the environment is seen as a sacred duty bestowed upon individuals who are considered as guardians and messengers of Allah. Hence, it is imperative for Muslims to acknowledge their responsibility as custodians of the Earth and actively ensure its welfare and

preservation (Mostafa, 2016). In the Islamic faith, it is considered that it is the responsibility of human people to safeguard and conserve the environment as a divine mandate from God. It is incumbent upon individuals to exert effort in safeguarding and fostering the globe, while refraining from jeopardizing the natural ecosystem. Thus, under Islam, the connection between mankind and the natural world is characterized by principles like as stewardship, obligation, and accountability towards the environment (Ghazali et al., 2018). In Islam, the connection between mankind and the natural world is determined by the principles of caretaking, responsibility, and environmental stewardship. The connection between mankind and the natural world in Islam is characterized by caretaking, a feeling of duty, and environmental stewardship. Stewardship refers to the connection between humans and the natural world, including a duty to take care of the environment.

Islamic Perspective: Management and Responsibility towards the Environment

The link between mankind and the natural world in Islam is characterized by a strong feeling of stewardship and concern for the environment. In Islamic theology, people are seen as celestial envoys entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and nurturing the planet. By adhering to the divine principles of equilibrium, Muslims assume the role of custodians who safeguard the world. This entails refraining from engaging in activities that pose a threat to the natural environment, such as deforestation, littering, and the discharge of pollutants. Muslims are also urged to embrace a sustainable lifestyle and actively engage in eco-friendly endeavors. Through embracing their responsibility as custodians of the Earth, Muslims may diligently supervise and safeguard the planet for the benefit of future generations. Furthermore, the notion of sustainability is well ingrained in Islam (Ghazali et al., 2018). The essay underscores the need of maintaining equilibrium between economic advancement and environmental preservation, so assuring the sustainable use of resources. In Islam, people are seen as stewards of the world since they have the responsibility to safeguard and nurture the environment. It is their duty to coexist peacefully with all of God's creatures and to ensure that their actions do not cause hurt or destruction. In Islam, the

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interaction between individuals and their environment is determined by the notions of governance, obligation, and responsibility. Consequently, Muslims are obligated to diligently safeguard the environment and shield it from deterioration. Islamic teachings establish a connection between mankind and the natural world via the principles of stewardship and environmental care. As stewards of the planet, Muslims are obligated to safeguard and enhance the environment (Mostafa, 2016). By behaving in this manner, people not only fulfill their religious obligations but also enhance the environment and the welfare of future generations. In Islam, the connection between people and their environment is determined by the notion of guardianship and care. As Muslims are divinely assigned by Allah as custodians of the planet, it is their responsibility to safeguard the environment and maintain equilibrium. In Islam, stewardship and responsibility pertain to the connection between mankind and the natural world. It is the duty of people to safeguard their environment.

The Role of Islamic Leaders and Academics in Environmental Advocacy

The involvement of Islamic leaders and scholars is essential for safeguarding sustainable practices and the environment (El-Sherbini et al., 2023). Historically, they have been trailblazers in safeguarding the environment and natural resources while promoting sustainable Islamic principles. Islamic leaders and scholars have the ability to motivate others to actively engage in environmental conservation initiatives by leveraging their influential roles and teachings. They may provide guidance on Islamic principles that safeguard the environment and offer pragmatic remedies to address environmental issues. The link between people and their environment in Islam is defined by the role of being a caregiver, responsible for maintaining and regulating the environment. Islamic leaders and scientists have a duty to safeguard the environment and advocate for sustainable practices. They should use their authority to promote consciousness and unite

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citizens in order to save the environment and guarantee its enduring viability. In Islam, the responsibility of being a caregiver and the relationship between humans and the natural world is characterized by the need to conserve and safeguard the environment. Islamic leaders and scholars possess the jurisdiction to safeguard the environment and advocate for sustainable practices. Islam highlights the need for individuals to safeguard and foster the globe. They have a crucial function in advocating for environmental responsibility and engagement within Muslim communities, as well as in cultivating proactive sustainable ideals. Islamic leaders and academics play a vital role in promoting the sustainability of Islamic basic beliefs by highlighting the necessary actions to safeguard the planet. Ghazali et al. (2018) advocate for sustainable approaches, emphasizing the significance of environmental conservation and safeguarding. Islamic leaders and scholars possess influential positions and knowledge that enable them to promote environmental conservation and motivate others to engage in proactive measures for protecting the environment (El-Sherbini et al., 2023). Islamic leaders and scholars consistently prioritize the promotion of core Islamic principles and the responsibility of mankind to safeguard the Earth. They have the ability to inspire individuals and communities to coexist harmoniously with nature and embrace sustainable practices for environmental preservation. Islamic leaders and scholars have played a crucial role in ensuring the long-term preservation of fundamental Islamic principles by highlighting the need of individuals to save the environment. They possess the capacity to inspire individuals and communities to coexist harmoniously with the natural environment and embrace sustainable practices that promote environmental preservation, while also ensuring they fulfill their responsibilities as faithful Muslims and conscientious caretakers of the planet. The creation of it is seen as a duty to safeguard and conserve the environment (Ghazali et al., 2018). In Islam, the connection between people and their creations is determined by the notion of stewardship, which entails the obligation to care for the environment in a responsible manner. In Islam, the connection between people and animals is determined by the notion of stewardship and the obligation to care for the environment. This highlights the crucial significance of conserving and safeguarding nature as an essential duty of Muslims. In Islam, the connection between people and their creatures is

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defined by the notion of stewardship and environmental care. This underscores the inherent duty of Muslims to save the environment. In Islam, the notion of stewardship and environmental care exemplifies the link between people and their creations. It underscores the utmost significance of conserving and safeguarding nature as the foremost responsibility of Muslims. In Islam, the connection between mankind and its creatures is defined by the notion of guardianship and care for the environment. This underscores the inherent duty of Muslims to save the environment. In Islam, the idea of stewardship and environmental care illustrates the link between people and their creations. This demonstrates that the first responsibility of Muslims is to conserve and safeguard the environment.

The need for eternal life is an unattained yearning of humanity. Religions have assuaged individuals' need for immortality and maintained their psychological well-being by positing the concept of an everlasting existence after death. According to the Holy Quran, "Every living organism will experience death." Every individual who tries to discover a method to achieve immortality will ultimately succumb to death. Mortality is an inescapable conclusion inherent in the human condition, and despite relentless efforts, individuals are unable to attain eternal life. The Holy Quran declares that death will inevitably reach individuals regardless of their location, even if they are inside fortified and secure structures. It demonstrates that mankind's aspiration for eternal life is a fruitless endeavor.

4- Desire to Hide and Suppress Death

An individual's contemplation of mortality is absent, as they dedicate themselves to many interests and endeavors. There is a complete absence of death intervals. Suppressing death is excluding death from one's future goals. The inclination of older individuals to accumulate their wealth and their reluctance to donate money to others exemplify death denial. Individuals have a reluctance to

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recall and discuss mortality, as seen by their actions. As a result, they refrain from using the word "deceased" to refer to an individual. They mitigate the concept of death by using phrases like "He lost his life" or "He passed away".

The one who expresses annoyance upon seeing the lyric "Every living thing will taste death..." is actively repressing and disregarding the concept of mortality. These comments clearly convey the concept of repressing death and treating it as a forbidden topic. Death being institutionalized is another contributing factor to its taboo status. The institutionalization of death is evident in several aspects, including the emergence of funeral service firms in some western nations, the detachment of individuals from the funeral and death processes, and the limited visibility of the operations performed on terminally ill patients until their demise.

5- Desire to Defy Death

The pursuit of immortality seeks to encounter the swiftest and most intense moments, since individuals are profoundly influenced by their experiences. This is the impact that contemporary superheroes and heroes, such as Himen, have on individuals. Ulubathı Hasan, Hz. Ali, and Hz. Our courageous individuals, such as Hamza, fearlessly faced death in order to attain martyrdom. Within our religious beliefs, martyrdom is seen as a position of great admiration and reverence. According to the Holy Quran, while humans see them as dead, they are really living. Accounts of martyrdom throughout Islamic history, as well as references to martyrdom in our epics and the Holy Quran, act as a catalyst for individuals' will to confront mortality.

6- Don't Want Death

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Although death is a circumstance that an individual may directly want, it is also conceivable for an individual to wish death. Consequently, an individual may want death as a result of a circumstance stemming from their innate drives. Freud discusses human inclinations, including the innate human need for survival and the inclination to revert back to non-living matter. As a result of this strong longing, an individual may yearn for death. Certain individuals may resort to suicide as a means to induce guilt in others, prompting them to attribute the cause of death to themselves. This act is occasionally seen as a resolution to interpersonal issues and disputes. Individuals with profound physical disabilities or those who have been victimized may have feelings of worthlessness, leading them to want death. In particular, in nations where materialism and scientific principles are highly revered, a lack of tolerance for the challenges of life might lead to instances of suicide. Nevertheless, death might be seen as a means to evade insurmountable bodily and psychological afflictions. Moreover, a Sufi who has a profound devotion to divine love may want for death as a result of their longing to encounter Allah.

7- Accepting Death

Typically, those who assess their life positively and aesthetically confront death with composure. Individuals' religious beliefs shape their emotions of serenity, acquiescence, and embrace while confronting mortality. However, the specific attributes of the religion being followed, an individual's religious convictions, and their level of commitment to their obligations seem to be significant factors in this matter. Hence, it is not reasonable to anticipate the same behavior across all faiths. The Holy Quran also stipulates the need of embracing mortality.

An individual who follows the Islamic faith acknowledges that they were created by Allah and that they will inevitably be reunited with Him. The verse "When a calamity befalls them, they say, "Indeed, we belong to Allah and we shall certainly return to Him"" indicates that when people face

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a disaster, they acknowledge their affiliation with Allah and express their belief in returning to Him. Muslims possess a constant readiness for mortality and see the earth as a realm for the hereafter. Our prophet instructed us to live in this world as if we were traveling or residing in a foreign land. Consider yourself among the individuals present at the graveyard. Avoid engaging in self-dialogue over the evening until you have completed your supper. Phrases like "Seize the opportunity to enjoy good health before falling ill and make the most of life before facing death..." serve as a reminder to believers to acknowledge the inevitability of death and prepare themselves for it.

Islam actually opposes the process of planning for death, instead emphasizing the need of embracing it. Belief in the afterlife is one of the fundamental tenets. Upon declaring oneself a Muslim, one acknowledges the inevitability of mortality. Hertz. In an alternate account from the Prophet, Ibn Umar said, "Rasulullah "I was in his company," he states.

A guy belonging to the Ansar community approached Hz and made an inquiry. He saluted the Prophet. Subsequently, he addressed the Prophet by saying, "O Messenger of Allah! Who among the believers is considered superior? The Prophet said that people who possess the highest moral standards. He inquired, "Among the believers, who possesses superior intellect?" "Individuals who have made adequate preparations." "They are the most intelligent," he said.

THE SITUATION OF THOSE WHO LOST THEIR LOVED PEOPLE FACED BY DEATH

1- Grieving

Mourning after the death of a "significant other" is a customary reaction.

The death of a loved one elicits innate responses in human nature. These emotions often lead to

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feelings of sorrow, mourning, and discontent. Grief is intricately linked to an individual's psychological state. According to Erol Göka, grief is an essential and unavoidable process. Our psyche is compelled to acknowledge realities that might be incredibly challenging. With age, individuals come to comprehend and embrace the fact that life is mostly outside our influence. He comprehends the inherent autonomy of life and acknowledges that many alterations will occur beyond our control. Embracing the realities of our human nature in life fosters our development and maturation. Another compelling justification for the need of grieving is that a significant loss may serve as a catalyst for human maturation, advancement, and rejuvenation.

Each narrative signifies the individual's progression towards greater humanity and their increased contribution to the collective human experience. According to him, challenges foster personal growth.

Elizabeth Kübler-Ross conducted studies on individuals facing a terminal illness. She found that self-punishment is a coping mechanism used by those who have lost a loved one, as a way to lessen the expected guilt and responsibility they feel for the death. According to her, engaging in the process of mourning would aid in her resolution of guilt and facilitate her healing. Mortality and the process of mourning are universal experiences. Experiencing the loss of a loved one evokes feelings of sadness in every individual. It is beneficial to understand that the feelings and actions seen in individuals who are experiencing sadness and grief are also encountered and shared by others in similar circumstances. Given that mortality is a universal experience, it does not have an impact on an individual's psychological well-being. The predominant feelings experienced upon an individual's death are sorrow and distress.

2- Denial

Assigning the cause of death to loved ones or oneself may be challenging. The individual has a

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simultaneous affection and unwillingness to acknowledge this reality. These claims are false and lack veracity. He vehemently rejects the concept of mortality and adamantly refuses to acknowledge its existence, using various phrases to convey his denial. Upon learning of death, an individual experiences a profound shock, feels emotionally numb, and resists accepting its reality. The individual may also encounter sensations of alone and sluggishness.

It is typical for an individual to experience shock and fatigue for a duration of many weeks. Nevertheless, the state of denial and disbelief might last for a prolonged period of time, spanning many days. An individual who rejects the death of a family member either expresses a lack of desire to participate in the funeral proceedings or exhibits a reluctance to take responsibility for its organization. He asserts that his beloved is deceased. He actively avoids contemplating mortality and engages in other activities as a kind of distraction from the subject.

3. Ambiguity: The loss of a loved one intricately entangles people's emotions. He experiences a range of emotions including fear, sadness, offense, doubt, relief, anger, and happiness. There is an inverse relationship between their happiness levels.

He is capable of expressing laughter or tears spontaneously. Therefore, differentiating between these feelings is challenging. When an individual's attention is diverted, even little choices may become challenging. Occasionally, he may exhibit a lack of desire to do even a basic duty. Even a little purchase might have significant implications. Decisions that were taken effortlessly before to the bereavement might escalate into significant challenges after the demise. Immediately after the demise, the surviving individuals experience a state of profound astonishment. They are unable to come to terms with the fact that a someone has passed away. Subsequently, the individual experiences a range of intricate feelings including apathy, insensitivity, astonishment, apprehension, perplexity, voidness, insignificance, and disorientation. During this phase, the

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individual may also have intense bouts of crying.

Throughout the moment of death, individuals may express regrets about their past actions, uttering statements such as "I wish I had refrained from certain behaviors" due to specific choices made throughout their lifetime. For instance, if a youngster desires his mother's demise because he is unable to fulfill his own needs, the child will have significant psychological distress in the event of his mother's death. Regardless of the time that has passed since he made the statement, the youngster is nonetheless impacted by it and bears ongoing responsibility for his mother's death. He will inform people, "I am responsible for this, my mother's demise was a consequence of my actions, I exhibited negative behavior, and my mother abandoned me." Similar to this youngster, individuals experience feelings of shame when they mistreat someone in their inner circle and that person subsequently passes away.

5- Anger

The two phases of protest are initial indignation and sustained fury. It is conceivable to have anger towards someone who has passed away due to their departure. He may experience anger in response to actions that were performed or should not have been performed. This animosity has the potential to propagate to other individuals. The elderly individuals begin to inquire as to the reasons for the demise of their beloved acquaintances.

Their inquiry pertains to the reason behind the demise of my relative as opposed to another individual. They have a negative response towards the doctor who is unable to save the lives of their beloved ones and may perceive that their patients are not receiving enough attention.

6- Bargaining

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The marketing phase is the ultimate assessment of both producers and customers. This is a disorder that specifically manifests in people who are in the latter stages of a terminal illness. Rather than passively awaiting the recovery of their own ailments or those of their loved ones, they actively seek a resolution with the divine being. They extol the Creator by asserting that if he remains immortal, I will dutifully serve him. They concur with the Creator to anticipate the reappearance of the one they hold dear. Individuals who are experiencing grief engage in prayer as a means to ascertain the survival of their beloved. They beseech both the Creator and the departed to preserve their existence. Additionally, it is suggested that this stage helps facilitate the recuperation of those who have experienced the loss of a family member.

7- Depression

Individuals who have experienced the loss of a loved one may often undergo these phases if they are unprepared for death, if the death was sudden, and if they have not acquired religious knowledge. The negotiation became unsuccessful, and the dead individual did not come back. Thus, it gradually takes root in the psyche of the bewildered individual.

The mourner acknowledged the veracity. Now, an individual may experience feelings of depression.

During the depressive phase, individuals often experience feelings such as weeping, despair, a sense of detachment from reality, social isolation, solitude, indifference, discontent, and sorrow. Depression is the term used to describe a state of profound sadness. A person may experience several states owing to this melancholy and loss. Throughout this process, an individual may alter their interpersonal connections with acquaintances and family members. Individuals with this condition may exhibit exaggerated emotional responses and demonstrate animosity towards certain individuals, experience a decline in their ability to participate in social interactions, and engage in

self-harming behaviors that are not intended to be fatal.

8- Acceptance

Upon traversing these phases, one comes to the realization that death is the only alternative. Coming to terms with the fact that a beloved someone has passed away marks the first stage of the recuperation journey. The individual has now attributed significance to the demise of their family member inside. He now begins to repair himself. He starts a process of reevaluating his connections, resulting in a significant shift in his perspective towards life, which becomes noticeably less gloomy. The period of being loved entails being disoriented and adjusting to the unfamiliar circumstances.

The individual who has experienced the loss of a family member progressively becomes integrated into a fresh network of connections and subsequently rebuilds their sense of self within the unfamiliar surroundings. Irrespective of the circumstances surrounding the dead, regardless of the level of acceptance by the individual, there will always be a sense of sadness present. Life is characterized by both peaks and valleys. Once again, he may experience sadness when a recollection of a departed somebody arises in his thoughts, when he visits a location associated with that person, or when he encounters one of their possessions.

What should be the attitude of a Muslim towards death?

Mortality is an inescapable fate that awaits all living beings. Mortality is an impartial examination that applies to every person, however the encounter and obstacles encountered by each people may vary. Hence, it is universally applicable.

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Each individual is allotted a finite duration known as a lifespan, which ultimately concludes with the event often referred to as death. According to the Holy Quran, each country is predetermined to have a certain duration of time. When their period arrives, they must not lag behind even for one instant, nor may they progress. Their countenances unmistakably disclose this veracity. Hence, it is imperative for Muslims to always bear in mind the inevitability of death and make adequate provisions for it. The Muslim perspective entails embracing death with serenity and making adequate preparations for its inevitability.

As previously said, those who lack religious development have distinct reactions to death, often experiencing depression and struggling to find meaning in their life when confronted with an unforeseen loss. The manner in which Muslims perceive the religion of Islam with regards to death is likewise the manner in which they interpret it with regards to life. Comprehending the concepts of life and death is equivalent. Individuals who have not fully accepted the concept of mortality and who lack a sense of tranquility about death have consistently experienced fear towards it and had challenges in coping with unexpected demises. To the sacred Quran and the Prophet. Reflecting on mortality and making preparations for it is a commendable practice when it is instructed and carried out, as shown by the life of the Prophet.

Remembering Death

Death signifies the termination of an individual's portion of earthly existence. An individual's test concludes with their death, thereby revealing the significance of their actions, both virtuous and malevolent, throughout their lifetime. In the afterlife, individuals will be rewarded or punished based on their behavior. By contemplating mortality and the existence after death, individuals might regain composure and inner strength. Upon a person's demise, there exists neither a time before nor a moment succeeding. Given the uncertainty of one's mortality, it is essential for an individual to consistently bear in mind and make necessary arrangements. Hertz. During the

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Prophet's presence among his companions, he drew lines on the ground and explicitly said, "These represent the aspirations and cravings of mankind, while this signifies their inevitable demise." As an individual advances in their dream realm, the nearest threshold of mortality materializes in front of them. Hence, being well equipped for mortality in any circumstance will always be advantageous to the individual. The Holy Quran addresses those who have embraced faith, stating, "O you who have believed! Be cautious of Allah, and have reverence for Allah, and be wary of Allah since Allah is fully cognizant of all your actions. The statement asserts the need of making arrangements for one's demise. It is important to have in mind mortality as a means of readying oneself for the inevitable end and the subsequent existence beyond. According to the Prophet, it is important to remember death as it serves as a powerful reminder of the hereafter and has the ability to diminish worldly joys. Death is considered the most tangible reminder of the existence of life beyond death, therefore motivating us to always keep it in mind. An Ansar friend inquired of the Prophet, "Who among the believers is the most sagacious?" "O Messenger of Allah?" he said, "Are those individuals who frequently contemplate mortality and diligently ready themselves for the hereafter considered the most sagacious?" He underscored the need of adequately preparing for the future and maintaining a steadfast remembrance of it. Regarding the inquiry of who is the most austere individual? The most austere individuals are those who constantly remember the decaying nature of the tomb, forsake superfluous worldly embellishments, prioritize the hereafter above the present life, and see themselves as part of the deceased. In Islamic belief, it is more beneficial to prepare for death and maintain a continual awareness of its inevitability, rather than relying on psychological theories to alleviate the fear of death. An individual who maintains a state of tranquility towards death and consistently keeps it in mind is very improbable to experience depression when faced with mortality. According to Islamic beliefs, the psychology of death is considered to be an eternal process. Individuals see death as an inherent component of existence and an organic phenomenon that may befall us. Rather than harboring fear towards death, it is crucial to cultivate preparedness and embrace its inevitability in one's consciousness. Hz. The Prophet regularly contemplated mortality and visited the cemetery on a regular basis. "Hello to

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you, nation of individuals who have faith!" "You have finally experienced the anticipated outcome," he said.

Currently, no future date has been authorized to be established. We anticipate being with you in the near future. His countenance effectively exemplifies to believers the appropriate disposition to adopt towards mortality and existence. He consistently emphasized to believers the need of often contemplating mortality, asserting that by doing so, they would lead a more fulfilling existence by achieving equilibrium between the awareness of death, appreciation for life, and concern for mortality.

Death marks both the final destination and the first stage of the transition to the afterlife. Thus, prior to confronting imminent demise, an individual need to ready their psyche for the inevitability of death, often contemplate its occurrence, and make necessary arrangements to alleviate anxieties and apprehensions.

Not Wishing for Death

Humans were created by God to undergo testing in an everlasting and infinite realm. Property, children, marriage, and relationships are all aspects that are subject to evaluation in this society. Consequently, the death of an individual is also an examination. The circumstances surrounding his death, including the location, cause, and age at the time of death, remain unknown to us. An individual is prone to encountering many challenges and hardships during their lifetime. The loss of his father might serve as a trial for him. The loss of his kid may provide a significant challenge for him.

The occurrence of irrational calamities such as sickness, starvation, and poverty are conceivable. At times, it may be incredibly challenging to withstand these hardships, leading individuals to

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experience depression. When confronted with these calamities that befall individuals, many of them may express their discontent with their existence. Individuals may contemplate suicide due to their inability to cope with the challenges of existence. The exact time and location of a person's death remain unknown. Postponing one's death is likewise strictly prohibited. Similarly, it is prohibited to anticipate death, meaning to want or long for death. According to the teachings of the Prophet, it is advised not to want death just due to experiencing a calamity. If he feels compelled to express the following sentiment: "O Allah, grant me a lifespan that is beneficial for me, and bring about my demise when it is advantageous for me." He deemed it inappropriate to seek death in the midst of adversity and challenges. Once again, the Prophet said, "It is not advisable for any of you to desire death." Avoid prematurely summoning death. As the deceased individual's actions cease, their legacy concludes. Existence enhances the well-being of the one who believes. He said that cultivating aspirations for a prosperous and enduring existence would be advantageous for those of faith. When individuals are confronted with the hardships and obstacles of life, they may see death as an escape route. While a few companions encountered this circumstance in the era of the Prophet, he cautioned them against it.

Showing Patience to Death

The Holy Quran identifies those who demonstrate fortitude throughout times of adversity, sickness, and conflict as virtuous. Individuals in our earthly existence are exposed to many examinations. Individuals are sometimes subjected to tests including either an excess or a deficiency of resources, apprehension, starvation, deprivation of possessions, and fatalities. Exercising patience is crucial during this examination. Mortality is a trial that deeply saddens human beings, often causing them to struggle with patience.

Human people want to lead lives characterized by robust health and tranquility. However, individuals may sometimes come into contact with a range of illnesses. While many illnesses are

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manageable, others are incurable. This may result in the individual experiencing psychological and physiological damage and anguish. The Prophet consoled the distressed and afflicted believers by affirming that Allah, in His infinite mercy, pardons the sins of a Muslim even for little afflictions such as a thorn piercing their foot, or for more significant hardships that they may endure. The transgressions of that individual who follows the Islamic faith fall like foliage off a tree. Therefore, Prophet Muhammad conveyed this positive information to those who shown perseverance. Certain companions would request prayers from the Prophet when they became ill. In response, our Prophet would offer them the option of praying for their sins to be absolved and for them to attain paradise through patience, or for their ailment to be healed. Indeed, umm is one of the friends. When Zufer, a lady afflicted with epilepsy, sought the prophet's intercession, she requested prayers. The Prophet, in his wisdom, proclaimed that those who possess the virtue of patience would be rewarded with eternal bliss in paradise. However, if you still want it, I beseech Allah Almighty to bestow upon you healing. He gave himself the freedom to make a choice. The woman's friend likewise opted for patience. The Companions shown both resilience and endurance when faced with life-threatening illnesses, as well as while dealing with the loss of a loved one. Undoubtedly, it is natural for an individual to experience sadness, to weep, and to shed tears when confronted with mortality. However, it is imperative to exhibit resilience and avoid excessive emotional display. Indeed, Hz. When he received the news of the death of the Prophet's grandson, he addressed his daughter, stating, "Allah Almighty is the ultimate authority in bestowing and taking away." Every event has a certain duration in the perspective of the divine.

He provided solace to him by advising, "Let him exhibit patience and anticipate his recompense from Allah." Once again, as he approached his daughter, Hz, he was overwhelmed with grief and tears welled up in his eyes. The Prophet said that the sensation of mercy is a divine gift bestowed onto the hearts of Allah's followers. Therefore, according to the teachings of the Prophet Muhammad, it is permissible within the bounds of Islam to express grief via tears at the passing of a loved one, as long as one refrains from using disrespectful or defiant language. This allowance is

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rooted in the recognition of the inherent emotional needs of human beings.

Ultimately, it is unattainable for individuals to escape mortality. The purpose of religion is to guide individuals in attaining inner tranquility via embracing mortality and leading a harmonious existence with the concept of death. If an individual does not have a harmonious relationship with death, they will not experience peace. While he may not be concerned about it throughout his youth, as he ages and approaches the end of his life, the aforementioned concerns and anxieties will inevitably encompass him. Human beings are inherently powerless when confronted with mortality, hence they must acquire the ability to coexist peacefully with the inevitability of death. A Muslim exhibits remarkable resilience and composure when confronted with mortality, fulfilling the inherent obligations dictated by their nature. An individual who maintains equilibrium between the mortal realm and the realm beyond, or the equilibrium between vitality and mortality, experiences well-being and serenity in both their spiritual and physical state.

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SECOND PART

DEATH AND LIFE AFTER

About the Moment of Death

Death is a phenomenon created by God. It refers to the cessation of life, the extinguishing of desires in the soul, and the absence of vitality in living beings. Death is the cessation of the life force and the separation of the soul from the physical body. Nevertheless, while examining the passages pertaining to the instant of death in the Holy Quran, there is an absence of explicit affirmation of the detachment of the soul at the precise time of death. Within the Holy Quran, there is no depiction of a human being with a divided nature, where the soul and body are distinct entities. Thus, the concept of the soul in the Quran aligns with what we refer to as the soul. If we acknowledge individuals possessing a soul as being alive, we must equally acknowledge those without a soul, namely those who have lost their soul, as dead.

As mentioned in the preceding sections, Spirit is the fundamental ingredient that bestows life and facilitates motion in people, distinguishing them as living beings. Hence, death denotes the detachment of an individual's soul. Death, like to life, is a phenomenon brought into being by a divine entity. Death, the antithesis of life, may be described as the cessation of the soul's wants and the termination of bodily functions necessary for life. Put simply, death is an inherent characteristic that signifies God's nullification of the ability to use the physical form He bestowed upon living entities. Having already provided biological insights into the process of death, we will now endeavor to provide knowledge in a tangible manner, as revealed in the Holy Quran and hadiths. Death, a profound occurrence, is a singular event that cannot be communicated by the one who experiences it.

There are several disagreements and confusions around the determination of death owing to the

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inherent difficulty in experiencing it and the intangible nature of the issue. The Holy Quran and hadiths provide insights into the precise circumstances surrounding the occurrence of death. Primarily, the Holy Quran consistently emphasizes the undeniable fact of mortality. Individuals earnestly contemplate this matter by drawing on their own encounters with mortality. "Mortality is an inevitable fate for all living beings." Be aware that the demise you continuously evade will inevitably catch up with you. Subsequently, you will be reunited with Allah, the omniscient being who has knowledge beyond human comprehension and perception. He will then disclose to you the actions you have undertaken. Despite the evident portrayal of this fact in the verses, when non-believers claim that Muslims would not have perished if they had heeded their advice, respond by challenging them to prove their sincerity by avoiding death themselves.

Furthermore, for those who have skepticism, He presents a thought-provoking proposition via the following verses: "Upon the arrival of the imminent demise, restore vitality." The Holy Quran also defies mortality. The statement unequivocally asserts that once death occurs, it is irrevocable and cannot be reversed by anybody. "However, when life becomes overwhelming, you find yourself in a state of helplessness." We have a closer proximity to it than you do, nevertheless, it remains imperceptible to you.

As you are not subject to anyone's authority, I implore you to revive life if you really stand by your words! Two hundred forty-eight These verses depict the last moments of a person's life, emphasizing that once death arrives, there is no possibility of return. People will be rendered powerless, but Allah will be in closer proximity to the deceased individual. In a separate set of lines, the statement is made: "No, it is now beyond the point of timeliness! When the soul reaches the throat, one can inquire, "Is there not a practitioner of healing present?" "Upon recognizing that this is the anticipated departure, and the legs are intertwined, the destination to which the patient is directed on that day is solely the presence of his Lord." It conveys the irrevocable nature of death.

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As the ill individual approach's death, their loved ones grow anxious and seek a remedy to prevent their family member from succumbing to mortality. In the middle of this haste, the individual who is on the verge of death becomes aware that it is now the moment to go from their loved ones and the materialistic existence.

At the conclusion, the soul departs. The tangling of the legs signifies that the departed individual has severed all ties with the earthly realm and is now being guided into the realm of the afterlife. Henceforth, the individual's autonomy is revoked. Certain scriptures indicate that a person on the verge of death communicates with celestial beings. "Those individuals who perish at the hands of celestial beings while engaging in self-destructive behavior, humbly submit and acknowledge, stating, 'We have not committed any wrongdoing.'" "Negative!" Allah has profound knowledge of your actions! As seen from the passage we cited, the individual on the verge of death will assert their innocence by claiming they have not committed any wrongdoing. However, the angels will not tolerate the malevolent individual and respond: "Allah is aware of your actions." Consequently, the evildoers will perish in anguish. These passages also indicate this. "The angels inflicted blows upon the faces and backs of the unbelievers, commanding them to experience the agonizing punishment of fire!" Imagine seeing the act of someone ending their life as a result of uttering these words! The angels' decision to end their lives may be attributed to their pursuit of actions that provoke Allah's displeasure and their aversion to actions that would bring Him pleasure. This is the reason why Allah rendered their actions futile. This passage explicitly highlights that sinners will face a dual punishment, with a portion occurring in the present world and the remainder in the hereafter. Furthermore, it suggests that individuals will experience this punishment at their demise and will pass away in a state of anguish. Once again, some individuals may want reprieve throughout the moment of their demise, although it will be denied to them. "Each of you shall face mortality, Oh God!" Prioritize allocating the resources we have provided you to assist others, rather than resorting to begging. Instead of requesting more time, express your intention to contribute willingly and exhibit altruistic behavior. When the appointed moment arrives, Allah does not delay

the demise of any individual.

Allah has complete knowledge of your actions. "Who is more unjust than someone who fabricates a falsehood about Allah, or someone who claims to receive divine revelation when they have not, or someone who asserts that they can produce something similar to what Allah has revealed?" As the oppressors faced imminent death, the angels extended their hands and urged them to rescue themselves. Today, you will face retribution in the form of humiliation due to your false statements about Allah and your haughty attitude towards His verses. If only you could see the consequences of your actions. Once again, it provides a clear and comprehensive explanation of the unfortunate demise of those who engage in sinful behavior. Once again, the angel of death summons the soul of an atheist upon their demise, with the words: "Depart, you impure soul." Manifest the divine anger and grief of Allah. He causes distress in his own life. The conversation between devout individuals who have faith and follow Allah's instructions with angels at the moment of death is documented as follows: "Those who have a reverential awe of Allah will be inquired about the revelations bestowed upon them by their Lord." According to them, he did not send it down. Favorable outcomes await those who engage in virtuous actions in this world. The dwelling place in the hereafter is superior. The abode of people who have reverence for Allah is very exquisite. The location they will access is a perpetual paradise with flowing rivers underneath; There, they will have all their desires fulfilled. This is the manner in which Allah will bestow rewards onto individuals who possess piety. The angels convey the message, "May peace be bestowed upon you; proceed to paradise in recognition of your deeds!" "They are the individuals to whom he will willingly relinquish his souls in a state of bliss." According to the Prophet, when a believer passes away and transitions to the afterlife, they are accompanied by several angels adorned in celestial garments and fragrances, as well as the angel of death. The angel of death is positioned next to the believer, while others are seated in close proximity. The angel of death beckons, "Oh satisfied spirit, emerge."

Embrace the benevolence and approval of Allah. The soul is effortlessly liberated, like to the

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effortless dripping of water from a container filled with water.

Angels may swiftly end your life.

The text elucidates the contrasting circumstances of nonbelievers and believers throughout the moment of their demise, asserting that nonbelievers would experience a distressing death, but believers will encounter a serene dying. During the moment of death, several remarkable occurrences will take place and individuals may express their desires. However, these factors will not alter the outcome. These admissions and flaws pertain to sinful individuals, whereas angels will not exhibit leniency towards them. These tales depict the anguish and spiritual torture that one may encounter throughout the process of dying. Simultaneously, details on the individual's location and circumstances at the moment of their demise are provided.

It is important to acknowledge that the experience of death varies among individuals throughout their lifetime. While one individual may die after an extended period of being confined to a bed, another one may have an abrupt demise.

An individual who has religious beliefs may encounter various challenges and ultimately pass away, while also potentially experiencing certain bodily ailments. It is unjust to see some individuals' physical conditions as a kind of divine retribution. Due to the unobservable nature of a person's moment of death, it is not possible to make conclusive conclusions. Only the knowledge supplied by the Holy Quran and hadiths may be used to reach certain conclusions on this issue.

Indeed, the Prophet Muhammad spent his last days in a condition of sickness, experiencing frequent episodes of fainting that rendered him unable to pray, ultimately leading to his death. The Holy Quran elucidates that once the state of intoxication caused by death occurs, there is no possibility of reversal. At this stage, the sensation of being intoxicated by death becomes an undeniable truth; "This is the very thing you continuously evade!" This stanza asserts that those who manage to evade death will eventually encounter the intoxicating effects of death. Upon the Prophet's demise,

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there was a vessel containing water in close proximity to him. The individual immersed his hand into the water, proceeded to apply it over his face, and engaged in prayer, reciting the following words: "There exists no deity except for Allah." Undoubtedly, there exists the intoxication of death. Regarding the Prophet's death, Hazrat Aisha clarifies that she does not feel any jealousy towards those who had a painless death, since she saw the immense sorrow, he had at his own passing. In another account, Hazrat Aisha said that the Prophet Muhammad died while he was positioned between her abdomen and the upper part of her chest. Based on my observations of the Messenger of Allah, I find it difficult to see death as a repulsive experience for anybody.

The Surah An-Nahl states that the life of believers would be taken effortlessly and that they will experience serenity and kindness. This highlights the fact that even the prophets endured suffering during their last moments. According to Islamic thinkers, the prize of death might vary for each individual, just as their tests in life varies. The duration of each individual's life varies. His lifestyle, the challenges he faces, and his level of spiritual connection vary. Hence, the precise moment of demise varies for each individual. Although a person's life may abruptly end within a single second, they have the ability to spend several days in bed beside another individual.

Islamic scholars elucidated the factors that contribute to the variability of the dying process among individuals as follows. Primarily, God has the ability to subject an individual to the anguish of death as a means of elevating their spiritual state. It is possible for God to inflict suffering onto some individuals at the moment of their demise. Hertz. This is the cause of the anguish experienced by the prophets and virtuous individuals. The persistent pain of these individuals leads to their elevation in status in the eyes of Allah. Another possible explanation might be the allure of death, serving as a means of redemption for one's transgressions. Allah has the power to cause intense suffering and pain to His devoted followers, whom He cares for deeply and wishes to pardon for their transgressions. If a believer perseveres through all the agony and torment experienced in their earthly existence, even the anguish caused by a thorn piercing their foot, their transgressions will be expiated. Furthermore, even if they are devoid of any wrongdoing, their virtuous actions will be

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duly documented. We have received information from the Prophet. Regarding this matter, Hz. Omar stated: "If a believer still carries remnants of their sins that were not absolved by their virtuous actions and repentance during their lifetime, Allah will intensify their death throes." Consequently, his soul ascends to the celestial realm. When an individual who does not believe in God does a virtuous act in the world, God grants them a more peaceful death and thereafter condemns them to hell, since they have already got the recompense for their virtuous action in the world. Consequently, the concept of death remains incomprehensible to all individuals.

The statements on the essence of death are elucidations and prognostications derived from these passages of the Quran. The Holy Quran discusses the concept of death and the experience of dying in the mentioned verses. However, its purpose is not solely to provide an explanation of death, but rather to confront non-believers by recounting the process of dying. From the perspective of believers, the Quran aims to help them prepare for death in order to avoid any difficulties that may arise.

Promoting Environmental Education and Awareness

Through the incorporation of environmental education and awareness into the framework of Islamic teachings, individuals may be encouraged to make conscientious decisions and engage in behaviors that promote a more sustainable global environment. Education and knowledge assist individuals in acknowledging their duty to save the planet. By integrating Islamic ecological conservation concepts into the educational curriculum, students may cultivate a profound sense of responsibility towards the environment and actively engage in safeguarding and conserving it for posterity. The material is named "Promotion of Environmental Education and Awareness in the Islamic Context". In Islam, there exists a sense of duty and guardianship towards both people and animals. Safeguarding the environment is a primary obligation of Muslims in the Islamic faith. Furthermore, it is essential for Muslims to engage in communication and dissemination of

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information pertaining to the environment. This initiative enables the promotion of public consciousness about the significance of environmental preservation and the promotion of the implementation of sustainable practices within their locality. Conservation and safeguarding of the environment Preserving and respecting nature is a fundamental obligation for Muslims. In Islam, the connection between people and creatures is determined by the notions of agency and accountability. Muslims have a basic obligation to save the environment. In Islam, the connection between people and their creations is seen as a vital duty of Muslims to safeguard and conserve the environment. In Islam, the human's responsibility towards their creations is to safeguard and oversee the environment. This underscores the inherent duty of Muslims to conserve and safeguard the environment. In Islam, the human's responsibility towards their creations is to safeguard and oversee the environment. This underscores the inherent duty of Muslims to safeguard and conserve the environment. In Islam, the human's responsibility towards their creations is to safeguard and oversee the environment. This underscores the essential duty of Muslims to conserve and safeguard the environment. Within the framework of Islam, there exists a profound obligation between individuals and their creations. This underscores the essential duty of Muslims to safeguard and conserve the natural world. In Islam, there exists a moral obligation that governs the relationship between people and their creations. This underscores the essential obligation of Muslims to conserve and safeguard the environment. In Islam, the human's responsibility towards their creations is to safeguard and oversee the environment. Conserving and safeguarding the environment is the primary duty of Muslims. In Islam, the human's responsibility towards their creations is to safeguard and oversee the environment. This emphasizes the inherent duty of Muslims to conserve and safeguard the environment. In Islam, the human's responsibility towards their creations is to safeguard and oversee the environment. This underscores the essential obligation of Muslims to safeguard and conserve the environment.

The Role of Man as Environmental Responsible in Islam

In accordance with Islamic teachings, individuals are entrusted with the duty of conserving and safeguarding the environment. The divine mandate bestowed upon them was to exercise dominion over and cultivate the globe. This duty necessitates abstaining from causing damage to the natural environment or exploiting natural resources. These actions, such as the clearing of forests, improper disposal of garbage, and contamination with dangerous substances, are seen as morally wrong in Islam. Moreover, Islamic doctrines emphasize the notion that the cosmos, including the environment, was bestowed onto mankind as a sacred gift and the principle of sustainability. Thus, it is imperative for Muslims to actively engage in the conservation and propagation of environmental knowledge since it aligns with a core tenet of their faith. According to Mostafa (2016), Muslims have a responsibility to save nature as its guardians. Safeguarding the environment and nurturing it in harmony with the divine equilibrium is of utmost significance. Those who adhere to this obligation in Islam also fulfill the obligation of caliphate, which symbolizes the responsibility of serving as God's representative on Earth. Amane is renowned for their goal to save the Earth from annihilation, and in the realm beyond life, they will assume accountability for their deeds. Thus, in Islam, the connection between mankind and its creatures is delineated by the responsibility of stewardship and the significance of nurturing the environment. It underscores the utmost significance of conserving and safeguarding nature as the first obligation of Muslims. In accordance with Islamic doctrines, mankind is entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment, a task that they are obliged to accomplish. They are required to carry out this duty by taking proactive measures to safeguard and conserve nature, while refraining from activities that exploit resources or cause damage to the environment. Islam places immense importance on environmental conservation, as shown by Ghazali et al. (2018). Sustainability is deeply rooted in Islamic culture, whereas activities like pollution and deforestation are considered detrimental to the environment. This duty includes not just safeguarding the environment, but also actively enhancing it to preserve equilibrium and concord. The Islamic religion underscores the

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significance of human need to safeguard and administer the natural realm, acknowledging the relationship between mankind and the natural world. The Islamic religion emphasizes stewardship as a means to comprehend the relationship between mankind and the natural world. Additionally, it necessitates environmental stewardship and accountability. According to Islamic teachings, it is the duty of humanity to safeguard and conserve the environment in their role as custodians of the world. The Islamic religion highlights the interconnection between mankind and the natural world, emphasizing the need to save the environment and be conscious of our obligations. Within the Islamic faith, the connection between individuals and their surroundings emphasizes the notion of stewardship and the need to care for the environment. In Islamic theology, people are seen as custodians, specifically fashioned by the divine being to safeguard the world and its natural riches. In Islam, the link between mankind and the environment underscores the need of humans to safeguard and oversee the world and its natural resources, since this duty has been bestowed upon them by God. According to Islamic doctrine, humanity is entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the environment as bestowed by God.

Man's responsibility as the caliph (steward) of the earth in Islam

In Islam, individuals are regarded as Caliphs, signifying that they have been divinely designated to oversee and safeguard their surroundings. Given the perception of the natural environment as a sacred gift, it is the fundamental duty of humanity to safeguard and maintain the ecosystem. This responsibility entails refraining from detrimental acts such as deforestation, overuse of natural resources, and polluting of forests. Furthermore, according to the tenets of Islam, individuals will be held accountable for all their actions on the day of reckoning. This behavior has a detrimental impact on the ecosystem. Islamic teachings prioritize the significance of sustainable behaviors in order to save the world for future generations. Islam highlights humanity's duty for the environment. Muslims have the duty of safeguarding and conserving the environment as custodians

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of the land. Thus, it is incumbent upon individuals to refrain from engaging in any activities that may cause injury or deterioration to the environment (Mostafa, 2016). The relationship between mankind and the natural world emphasizes the idea of stewardship and environmental care in Islam (Ghazali et al., 2018). Muslims have the duty to uphold and advocate for the well-being and equilibrium of the environment as its custodians. According to Islamic teachings, it is expected that God would assist mankind in safeguarding the earth. Their duty includes safeguarding their resources, upholding the equilibrium and concord of the natural world, and averting any injury or deterioration to the environment. The notion of guardianship and safeguarding of the environment has great significance in Islam. Islam emphasizes the responsibility of humans as God-appointed guardians to conserve and safeguard the environment. The notion of accountability in relation to environmental stewardship is firmly ingrained in Islam. As God has designated this creed to safeguard the globe, individuals are regarded as caliphs. Islam ultimately requires mankind to assume the responsibility of becoming stewards or Caliphs of the world. The obligation is with them to conserve and safeguard the environment, guaranteeing its enduring preservation and sustainability. According to Islamic beliefs, people are seen as custodians of the world and are entrusted with the holy obligation of conserving and safeguarding the environment. In Islam, people are seen as integral components of the expansive ecosystem designed by God, and they are entrusted with the responsibility of diligently overseeing the world. During the day of reckoning, people will be held accountable for all their actions against their environment. Islam underscores the human need to save the environment (Ghazali et al., 2018). Consequently, under the Islamic faith, it is incumbent upon each person to save and defend the environment. Within Islamic doctrine, safeguarding and conserving the environment is seen as an integral aspect of the faith. In accordance with Islamic teachings, it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard and enhance the earth, as bestowed by God.

About the Confinement of the Soul

Spirit, often understood as the vital essence that animates humanity, is primarily used to refer to divine revelation, the Quran, and the angel Gabriel in the Holy Quran. Consequently, he had created a barrier that separated him from them. Subsequently, we sent our essence to him, and the ethereal being materialized before him, assuming the whole physical manifestation of a human being. "During that evening, the celestial beings and the ethereal entity descend to carry out their assigned duties under the authorization of their divine Master." Gabriel is referenced in his poetic lines. According to the Quran, we have communicated to you a spirit via our instruction. The passage further demonstrates that the soul symbolizes the Quran and divine revelation.

Hertz. In the passage, the Prophet is questioned on the soul: "They inquire of you concerning the soul." Declare: "The true nature of the soul is known only by my Lord, and you possess limited understanding." The soul is described as a metaphysical and imperceptible entity. According to several experts, the term "soul" in this context refers to the soul responsible for sustaining the physical well-being of the human body. However, the term "soul" in this context refers to the Jews inquiring about the source of the revelation from the Prophet. Gabriel is also referenced. Considering the prominence and circumstances surrounding the passage, here the term "spirit" does not refer to the entity responsible for sustaining human existence. The Holy Quran states that God bestows insight to his chosen followers in order to forewarn them of the day of encounter. By uttering this statement, Jesus once again used the term "spirit" to refer to a kind of divine disclosure. The designation of the Quran as the "spirit" might be considered a simile. In reality, similar to how the spirit rejuvenates lifeless bodies, the Quran similarly revitalizes dormant hearts. It rescues individuals from the state of ignorance that may be compared to death. and it guarantees that he will not experience restlessness in his everlasting existence. Put simply, the more significant the soul's role in animating the human body, the more crucial revelation becomes for the redemption, prosperity, and harmony of mankind. The shared characteristic of revelation and the soul is their ability to provide vitality. Indeed, the Holy Quran also states the veracity of this statement is shown

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via the following proclamation: "O believers, heed the call of Allah and His Messenger, as they invite you towards actions that bring vitality..."

In the hadiths, the term "spirit" is used to refer to Gabriel, as well as to denote the "Soul", which is the vital essence that animates human beings. Death is defined as the moment when the soul departs from the physical body. Thus, it may be said that human death transpires upon the apprehension of the soul. The phrase "the soul reaching the throat" in the poems signifies the time of the soul's departure from the body. According to the Holy Quran, the angel of death sent to you will cause your death, after which you will be brought back to your Lord. We are informed that the angel of death will seize the life, namely the soul, of an individual at the precise time of their demise. "He possesses exclusive authority and dominion over his subordinates."

He sent guardians to you. Ultimately, when the moment of death arrives for any individual among you, our messengers (the angels entrusted with this duty) carry out the task of taking their life... By use pluralization, it is indicated that there is not a solitary angel responsible for the act of taking life, but rather a collective of angels. In addition to the angel of death, these angels are understood to be angels associated with both punishment and compassion. The angels seem aesthetically pleasing to the faithful and communicate with him in the following manner: "Arise, contented spirit residing in the exquisite vessel, emerge with the glad tidings of divine benevolence and encounter your Lord," thereafter escorting his soul with elegance. According to this positive information, it is said that the believer would be exempt from experiencing the agony of death. When extracting the soul of a nonbeliever, he utters the phrase, "Depart, malevolent spirit from the malevolent body." They ensnare his tormented spirit by proclaiming, "Emerge debased and acclaimed with infernal glory." According to our Prophet, while discussing the conquest of the soul, he said the following: Bera bin Azib recounts, "We accompanied the Messenger of Allah to the burial ceremony of a man from the Ansar." Upon our arrival at the burial site, we saw that the grave had not yet been excavated. We took our seats beside the Prophet. We remained in a state of silence. Prophet Muhammad was blending the dirt with a wooden implement in his hand. Without warning,

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he abruptly lifted his head many times and uttered: "Take shelter in Allah to protect yourself from the agony of the grave!" He stated and subsequently remarked, "Upon the impending departure of the faithful from this earthly realm to the realm beyond, celestial beings adorned with countenances as radiant as the sun descend from the heavens. They bear shrouds and fragrances procured from Paradise and take their place beside the believer's bedside. They address the virtuous soul, urging it to depart and partake in the divine approval and absolution." The soul emerges out the container's mouth like to the flowing of water and is then seized by the angel of death. Instantaneously, prepared angels swiftly retrieve the soul of the faithful from the angel of death's possession and place it inside the shroud and fragrances they have provided. This results in a scent more exquisite than musk emanating from the soul, permeating the soil. Subsequently, the angels promptly elevate the soul. During the process of removing the souls of non-believers and wrongdoers, angels will manifest themselves to them in a frightening manner. Upon delivering the distressing news, the individual's soul will be extracted in a laborious manner, like to the arduous removal of a thorny iron from damp wool. The person's soul will be conveyed by the angel of death to the angels of agony, resulting in the emission of a foul odor from the soul of the unbeliever. When the angels transport this malevolent entity to the celestial realm and request the opening of the heavenly gates, they remain closed to this malevolent entity.

As previously said, although there are several accounts, it is understood that the souls of the virtuous and the wicked will be apprehended in distinct ways throughout the process of capturing an individual's soul. Given the intangible nature of capturing the soul, our understanding of this matter is limited to the insights provided by verses and hadiths.

About Grave Life

1-Perception of the Grave

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Currently, human people have abandoned their earthly attachments and have transitioned into the realm of the dead, a distinct and separate dimension. A grave is a designated location for interring deceased individuals, where their bodies are laid to rest and buried. It is also characterized as a unique dwelling location for mankind, beginning with death and lasting until the resurrection during the apocalypse.

When examining this term in the Holy Quran, it is referred to as "el-kabr", "al-mekâbir", and "el-kubûr". These terms signify the concept of a grave, the specific location where a grave is situated, and a cemetery.

The term "akber," derived from the same root, is referenced in the Qur'an as "Then he killed him and buried him." Commentators have interpreted the word "akber" in this verse to signify that he was inspired with the knowledge of how to bury him. The Holy Quran prohibits the act of praying for someone who has passed away or standing at their grave. They rejected Allah and His Messenger and died in a state of error. He thereafter designated the location where deceased individuals were interred as a grave. Once again, the phrase "they will be resurrected from their graves" is mentioned. In several passages of the Quran, the location where the dead is interred is referred to as the grave. According to Surah Abese, Allah is the one who imparts knowledge to human beings about the cemetery and motivates them to be buried in it. According to the Holy Quran, burying a human person under the earth is considered sacred. The origin may be traced back to Adam, Hz. The Holy Quran narrates the account of Adam's offspring in the following manner. Driven by his intense emotions, he ultimately succumbed to the need to murder his own brother, thereby joining the ranks of the disillusioned. A divine crow was sent by God to demonstrate the burial process for the user's deceased sibling. "I feel ashamed of myself!" "Am I as large as this crow and unable to bury my brother's corpse?" he said, expressing remorse for his actions. When examining the context of these passages, it is evident that Hz. Adam's two sons, Habil, and Cain, engaged in a dispute which ultimately led to Cain murdering Abel. He is uncertain about his course of action after the murder of his brother, and during this state of perplexity, God sent a crow from

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the heavens. The crow engaged in ground-scratching behavior and instructed his other tribesmen on the appropriate actions to take. According to an alternate speculation, it is believed that God sent a pair of crows, and one of the birds fatally attacked the other, after which the surviving crow proceeded to inter the deceased crow in the earth. Consequently, Cain acquired knowledge of the procedure for interring in the soil. In Surah Taha, Allah reiterates that He created humanity from a certain source, would eventually return them to it, and thereafter bring them out from there once again. He imparted this knowledge to human people by his authority.

2-Barzakh Realm

A partition is a physical or conceptual boundary that separates two entities. Indeed, in the Holy Quran, it is said that "He caused the convergence of the two seas." There is a barrier between them; They do not disrupt each other. "He is the one who has caused the convergence of two bodies of water, one fresh and satisfying, and the other salty and unpleasant, and has established a barrier, an impenetrable partition, between them." During the act of commanding, the obstruction present in this situation is referred to as an isthmus.

The word refers to the interval between death to resurrection, including the transition between the earthly realm and the afterlife. Within the context of the Holy Quran, it is said that when an individual is faced with death, they utter the words, "My Lord! Return me to my previous existence so that I may engage in benevolent actions in the world I departed from. Negative! His statement is only vacuous rhetoric. An isthmus lies ahead of them till the day of their resurrection. Upon the sounding of the trumpet, both their familial connections and their ability to engage in dialogue will become irrelevant. "Those individuals whose scales are weighted heavily will achieve success." It is mandated. As stated in this verse, the term "barzakh" refers to a realm or state that is believed to exist between life and afterlife, specifically within the context of the grave. It is a subject that elicits

many interpretations and perspectives.

According to some historians, the term was used in its literal meaning to refer to the barrier that separates death from a person's reentry into the world. Alternatively, other scholars defined it as the barrier that separates death from the day of resurrection. The term "isthmus" has been subject to several interpretations by academics. These include the time between the earthly life and the afterlife, the period between the sounding of two trumpets, or the duration in the grave between the earthly life and the afterlife. The period after an individual's death and separation from the earthly realm, extending till the end of existence, is referred to as the grave's existence or the barzakh realm. Regardless of whether they are buried or not, every individual is involved in the process of decomposition from the time of their death. Several writers have asserted that the isthmus process is neither a terrestrial process nor an afterlife process. Specifically, the isthmus refers to the transitional phase between the earthly realm and the realm of the afterlife. During this interval, the deceased are neither present among the living to partake in their meals and beverages, nor are they among the inhabitants of the hereafter to see the consequences of their actions.

As previously mentioned, the isthmus is seen to represent both the dividing line between death and resurrection, and the dividing line between death and the world. The isthmus, often seen as a hindrance, has also been construed as a transitional space. Following an individual's death, their soul will transition to a realm known as the barzakh or the world of spirits, where it will remain in anticipation of the day of resurrection. However, this departure will never reincarnate into the world with a new physical form. The individual's actions and evaluation phase have concluded, and now the era of awaiting responsibility has begun.

Examination of Verses That Point to Life in the Grave

1-Question of the Grave

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The Holy Quran does not explicitly address the subject of the grave, but it is mostly derived from narrations. The phrase suggests that people who have faith in truthful statements are steadfast in both their earthly life and the hereafter. Allah guides the wrongdoers astray and exercises His own will. This verse raises the issue of the grave. According to tradition, the Prophet spoke this passage in response to a query asked in the tomb. "When a devout individual is situated in their burial place, celestial beings approach them," they state. Subsequently, a person of faith affirms that there is no deity save Allah and that Muhammad is the Messenger of Allah. Upon perusing the aforementioned poem, the Divine Being said, "This verse elucidates the current circumstance." There is a lack of consensus among scholars over the interpretation of this passage. Tabari has two distinct perspectives on this matter. Initially, he asserted that attaining stability in one's earthly existence is intricately linked to the inquiry encountered in the tomb. Furthermore, Allah grants believers' steadfastness throughout the interrogation in the tomb, both in the present life and the hereafter.

Baghawi said that the questioning session would occur in the graves, and Allah will ensure its permanence. The majority of commentators opined that the judgment in the earthly realm will transpire throughout one's lifetime, while the judgment in the hereafter will occur in the graves. After elucidating this passage, the commentators who addressed the matter of the grave included Enes b. They had narration from Malik about the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). According to reports, he said that after a person is buried and their friends go, the deceased may still perceive the sound of their footsteps. The deceased is seated and questioned about their perception of Muhammad, the individual in question. The individual who is posed with this inquiry responds, "I bear witness that he is the Messenger and Servant of Allah." Divine beings: Examine the location of your designated place in the realm of eternal punishment. By divine intervention, Allah has transformed this site of suffering into a heavenly abode specifically for your benefit. And someone who has faith perceives both the concepts of hell and paradise simultaneously. Qatada states that it was communicated to them that the faithful person would be provided with enough room at their burial site. He then proceeds to resume the narrative of Enes. "Regarding the servant

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who displays hypocrisy and disbelief, he confesses I possess no knowledge concerning Him." "I would convey the remarks made by others about him," he responds. Subsequently, he is informed, "You failed to comprehend and comply" and strikes him forcefully with iron mallets, causing him to scream.

"All beings perceive this exclamation except for the two groups consisting of humans and jinn."

According to scholars, verse 14/27 of Surah Ibrahim addresses the concept of the cemetery. They have included the aforementioned narrations as an explanatory reference to this verse. In this instance, the terms "tawhid" and "martyrdom" have significant importance. The message is firmly implanted in the minds of people who have faith by Allah, the Supreme Being. It unites them by a shared belief in both the present existence and the existence after death. Believers are able to live a well-rounded existence in the world thanks to the ability to anticipate and be aware of future events that religion offers. Their existence in this realm also contributes to the attainment of salvation in the hereafter. Allah stipulates that a good word must possess a consistent and unchanging root. The defining traits of profanity include lack of roots and lack of consistency. Tawhid is a resolute and exquisite concept that endures as a truth throughout the believers' earthly existence, allowing them to attain Allah's benevolence and recompense in the hereafter. To assert that Allah bestows endurance implies granting perseverance as a method of attaining respect and reward. Hence, the implication is that their constancy persists not just in the present world but also in the realm after death. However, the text mentions both the earthly realm and the realm beyond death. In verses 24-26 of the Ibrahim Surah, Allah provides examples of both positive and negative words. In the 27th verse, Allah underscores the significance of the "Qawl-i Thabit," which refers to a steadfast and righteous word. This steadfast word serves as a means of redemption for the Believers, safeguarding them in both the present life and the hereafter.

Although this poem does not directly address the topic in the grave, it has been widely regarded by academics as being connected to that concept. The primary topic of discussion is on the caliber of

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the inquiry inside the tomb. Currently, there are divergences on the nature of the soul-body connection. The perspectives on this matter may be succinctly described as follows:

According to some individuals, life after death is purely spiritual, hence the process of questioning and seeking answers is only carried out by the soul. It is unrelated to the physical form. According to their perspective, hashr is not just a tangible entity. According to some individuals, existence in the dead encompasses a spiritual existence. Interrogations are directed at the soul while it resides in the tomb, however, the souls are subsequently reunited with their physical bodies during the process of resurrection.

According to many beliefs, throughout the afterlife, the soul undergoes a questioning process while the body remains in the grave, without the soul being reunited with it. The divine have the ability to respond to inquiries inside the physical form.

Consequently, two scriptures were used as substantiation for the serious inquiry, although these verses are not directly pertinent to the serious inquiry. Thus, the Holy Quran addresses the matter of the grave indirectly, using an interpretative approach. Nevertheless, by comparing the passage with the aforementioned genuine hadiths, it becomes necessary to acknowledge, as is commonly agreed upon by most commentators, that it pertains to the matter of the grave.

2-The Torment of the Grave

There is a lack of consensus among Islamic scholars about this matter. Commentators have asserted that the passages highlighting the disparity between the deaths and lives of those who engage in wicked actions vs those who do virtuous activities indicate the existence of agony in the tomb. Do individuals who are immersed in wickedness assume that we would treat their lives and deaths on par with those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions for both this world and the hereafter?

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"Their judgments are highly erroneous!" This passage implies that the demise and fate of those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions, both in this life and the hereafter, will not be equivalent to those who are deeply immersed in wickedness. Based on some interpretations.

As previously said, this implies that individuals will readily surrender their existence in the moment of death, and that rewards and punishments will promptly commence in the hereafter for devout and virtuous individuals.

Tabari and Zamakhshari omitted any reference to the punishment of the grave in their reading of this passage. Instead, they highlighted that both believers and those who defy Allah would face identical consequences, not only in this life but also in the hereafter. Although this line discusses the concept of rewards and punishments in the tomb, several interpreters have read it as referring to agony in the hereafter. While the passage alludes to the suffering in the dead, it does not provide substantial proof. Verse 93 of Surah An'am serves as an indication of the punishment that awaits in the tomb. Although the passage discusses the challenges that will be encountered at the moment of death, there are scholars who acknowledge that same difficulties will persist in the grave. "Who can be more unjust than those who claim to have received divine revelation and arrogantly declare that they will produce verses similar to those revealed by Allah, even though they have not received any revelation themselves?" As the oppressors faced imminent death, the angels extended their hands to save them and urgently urged them to preserve their lives. The statement conveyed that you would face a punitive and degrading agony today due to your false claims about Allah and your arrogance towards His verses. Zamakhshari refers to the instant of demise and the intense anguish experienced at that period when the phrase "you will be subjected to punishment" is spoken. Additionally, it may convey existence on the narrow strip of land and anguish at the end of the world. Ibn Atiyya interprets the angels' aggressive behavior against the oppressors as the first sign and precursor of the impending punishment. Bukhari presents this passage as the primary evidence for the concept of suffering in the dead, considering it very compelling. According to Tabari, the suffering of disgrace felt in this place is equivalent to the suffering of hell. Some argue

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that the term "today" in the poem refers to suffering in the grave, while others contend that it cannot signify pain in the tomb. According to other interpretations, the term "today" refers to the apocalypse and the afterlife, rather than the tomb and the isthmus.

This passage demonstrates that anguish and retribution may manifest in three distinct settings: the instant of demise, the burial site, and the realm beyond life. Each of them may entail adversity and retribution. Thus, although not definitive, it indicates the suffering experienced in the tomb. Chapter al-Mu'min, verses 45-46. According to the passages, the Pharaoh's dynasty was engulfed in flames both in the morning and evening. This is often regarded as one of the most compelling pieces of evidence for the existence of suffering in the tomb. "This person was safeguarded by Allah from the malicious schemes set against them, and a harsh punishment engulfed and annihilated Pharaoh's lineage." This agony refers to the intense suffering that individuals are subjected to both in the morning and evening. Upon the arrival of Doomsday, subject Pharaoh's family to the worst anguish and suffering. An audible outcry will be perceived. This line evokes the concept of the grave's anguish by referencing Pharaoh and his dynasty enduring perpetual exposure to fire, along with the anticipation of even more intense punishment in the future. Commentators argue that the reference to morning and evening in this context pertains to the earthly concept of morning and evening. However, they assert that discussing morning and evening in the afterlife is not feasible. Analysts assert that the fire mentioned in this passage refers to the fire of the barzakh, specifically denoting the pain experienced in the grave. This is because the soul is everlasting and serves as a sign of the suffering experienced in the tomb.

Tabari suggests that the phrase "being presented to the fire in the morning and evening" might signify the act of showing someone their designated position in hell as a means of shaming and condemning them. He fails to explicitly specify the exact details of the proposal. "Upon the demise of an individual, their destination and abode are unveiled to them both in the morning and evening." The locations of the inhabitants of heaven are revealed to those who are in heaven, whereas the locations of the inhabitants of hell are revealed to those who are in hell. He spoke to him, "This is

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your designated location."

According to belief, Allah will transport you to that place once the Day of Judgment concludes. The passage and the hadith pertain to the state of being subjected to the fire. Nevertheless, the meaning of this remains ambiguous. The prevailing consensus among scholars is that the reference to being exposed to the fire in the morning and evening in this passage signifies the punishment experienced in the grave. Thus, this the poem undoubtedly refers to the punishment experienced in the grave. Analysts interpret this line, which depicts the people of Noah perishing in water and thereafter being cast into the fire, as a sign of the suffering experienced in the grave. "They perished in the deluge as a consequence of their transgressions, subsequently being cast into the inferno, and were unable to procure any aid or guardianship against Allah." Analysts One of the reasons for the association of this passage with the pain experienced in the tomb is as follows: The abbreviation "fa" in the poem stands for follow-up. This should occur promptly upon submersion in water. Hence, similar to the global occurrence of drowning in water, the global occurrence of being tossed into the flames would likewise transpire. Consequently, the anguish of the burial was significant.

Zamakhshari asserts that this verse pertains to the concept of the afterlife, while others argue that it can potentially allude to the suffering experienced in the grave. They state the following: "Regardless of whether an individual perishes by drowning in water or being consumed by fire, or even if they are devoured by wild creatures and birds, they will still be subjected to the torment that befalls those interred in the grave." Consequently, an individual might experience the anguish of the cemetery without being buried in the soil.

Tabari and Baghawi assert that the intended meaning of this poem is inferno. Nevertheless, the majority of experts say that this passage is demonstrative of the anguish experienced in the dead. However, although the majority of commentators link the concept of the hereafter to the tomb, a few commentators link it to the afterlife.

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While the poem may suggest the possibility of representing the suffering experienced in the cemetery, its meaning remains ambiguous due to its lack of clarity.

The Holy Quran has several passages that explicitly state the occurrence of agony inside the tombs. Some of them provide a mild indication, while others definitely show suffering in the graves. Upon examining the passages and the interpretations of scholars, it becomes evident that the presence of the isthmus process, the questioning in the tomb, and the punishment in the cemetery are unquestionable.

3-Blessing of the Grave

Those who have faith in and follow Allah's instructions should expect to receive blessings and good tidings in the hereafter. Similarly, those who do not believe or defy authority are subjected to penalties. The Holy Quran questions if individuals who are immersed in wickedness believe that their lives and deaths will be equated with those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions, both in this world and the hereafter. Their assessments are very inaccurate! This stanza demonstrates the inherent inequality between the two classes in terms of death and isthmus.

According to some interpreters, the discrepancy between the good and the evil after death implies that those who commit crimes should experience both the anguish and blessing of the tomb simultaneously.

Within a different stanza, there should exist a divine favor, namely in the form of nourishment, bestowed upon the victims. Regard those who are slain in the cause of Allah as not dead! Contrarily, they are living and get pleasure from the nourishment bestowed upon them by Allah via His benevolence and compassion. They will get abundant nourishment from their divine Master.

They get pleasure from receiving the positive information that their future murdered brethren, who

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have not yet joined them, will be free from dread and grief. Refrain from using the term "dead" to refer to individuals who have been slain in the sake of Allah. Contrary to your knowledge, they are really living. According to Tabari, every individual's soul is inherently alive throughout the intermediate phase of existence. Martyrs are distinct from others in that they will get heavenly gifts even while they are still in the mortal realm. This bestows vitality to them. These words demonstrate the continued existence of the martyrs; however our comprehension is hindered by the limitations of the human intellect. The majority of experts acknowledge that the reference in these lines is to events occurring in the grave, and they substantiate this interpretation with narrations.

These lines demonstrate that both martyrs and all believers will receive rewards according with their status. The reference to only martyrs is attributed to their elevated status and the commendable nature of their participation in jihad. Alternatively, it was believed that this implied that only martyrs would be supplied. Nevertheless, this is a subjective view. According to the narrative, it is said that martyrs would get food and benefits in paradise. The notion of a blessing inside the tomb or isthmus is also included in the interpretation presented here. The spiritual tranquility of the martyrs is evident. Spiritual serenity or spiritual relief may also be present. Nevertheless, the bestowal of material plenty and alleviation in the tangible realm is contingent upon subjective interpretation. Hence, it is evident that there is a provision, while its true significance is known only to God.

APOCALYPSE AND RESURRECTION

Islamic Environmental Ethics and Pro-Environmental Behavior

The Islamic perspective on environmental ethics highlights the significance of effective management, responsibility, and accountability in order to save and conserve the environment (Gifford and Nilsson, 2014). This ethical concept is founded on the conviction that the Earth and

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its resources were bestowed to mankind by a divine entity and need safeguarding. Supposedly, mankind will face consequences on the day of judgment based on its level of success in fulfilling its duty to save the environment. In addition, Islamic teachings strongly prioritize sustainability and forbid activities that cause damage to the environment, including pollution, deforestation, and excessive exploitation of natural resources (Ghazali et al., 2018). According to Islamic teachings, it is the responsibility of people, who are seen as custodians of Allah, to safeguard and conserve the environment. In accordance with Islamic doctrine, mankind is entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the world as custodians appointed by God. In Islamic theology, the notion of the universe, including the environment, being seen as a divine gift has great significance. It is our solemn duty as custodians of God's creation to conserve and safeguard the environment. In accordance with Islamic doctrine, mankind is designated as custodians whom God has entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding the planet. In Islamic theology, people are seen as custodians entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the world as per divine decree. Man has been entrusted by God with the responsibility of overseeing and safeguarding the environment in order to promote its growth and preservation (Mostafa, 2016). Islam underscores the need for individuals to assume the duty of safeguarding the environment (Masturin et al., 2022). Muslims have a duty to safeguard and conserve the environment as custodians of the world (Mostafa, 2016). In Islam, the link between people and the environment is founded on the belief that God created the earth as a benevolent offering, and it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard it (Ghazali et al., 2018). According to Islamic teachings, mankind is entrusted with the responsibility to safeguard and advance the earth, as bestowed by God. In Islam, it is the responsibility of mankind to safeguard and maintain the environment, as ordained by Allah.

Man and his creation according to Islam

According to Islamic doctrine, humanity is entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and maintaining the Earth. Preserving and fostering the environment is their responsibility, seeing it as a sacred bestowment. They have a solemn duty to safeguard and maintain the environment, and they will be held responsible for how well they meet these commitments on the day of reckoning. Muslims have a duty to safeguard and conserve the environment as caretakers of the world (Mostafa, 2016). This encompasses the act of refraining from engaging in activities that cause damage to the environment, such as overuse of natural resources, emission of pollutants, and the clearing of forests. Moreover, Islam advocates for the dissemination of environmental knowledge to enhance environmental consciousness and accountability within Muslim populations (Saleh and Hasan, 2019). Islam asserts that humans, given their role as custodians of God's creation, have the duty to safeguard and maintain the environment (Ghazali et al., 2018). In Islam, people are seen as celestial envoys on earth and are entrusted with the duty to safeguard and preserve the environment. It is crucial for them to carry out their responsibilities as diligent leaders in order to guarantee the enduring viability of natural resources and the maintenance of equilibrium. In Islam, the connection between mankind and its creations is seen as a partnership where people are entrusted with the duty to nurture, be answerable for, and assume accountability for. Within the Islamic faith, individuals have a moral duty to save the planet and must actively preserve and foster the natural surroundings. In Islamic religion, the link between humanity and the environment is based on the concept that God created the world as a precious gift and entrusted human beings with the duty of safeguarding it. In Islam, the link between mankind and the environment is based on the belief that God created the planet as a benevolent gift and entrusted people with the responsibility of safeguarding it. In Islam, the connection between mankind and its creation is determined by the notions of governance, obligation, and responsibility. In Islam, Allah has bestowed upon people the responsibility of safeguarding and maintaining the environment. Humans have been entrusted by God with the responsibility to effectively manage and safeguard the environment. In Islam, mankind is

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designated by Allah as custodians with the responsibility of conserving and safeguarding the environment. In Islam, the responsibility of safeguarding and preserving the environment is considered a divine obligation bestowed upon individuals. According to Islamic teachings, humanity is entrusted by God with the duty to safeguard and preserve the environment. In Islam, it is the divine mandate of Allah for mankind to safeguard and maintain the integrity of the environment. The user's post is devoid of any content. In Islam, the responsibility to safeguard and maintain the environment is assigned to Allah. In Islam, mankind has been designated by God as stewards with the responsibility to oversee and safeguard their environment. This pertains to the connection between human beings and God and the entities He has brought into existence. In Islam, the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the environment is bestowed upon humanity by God. In Islam, the connection between people and creatures is determined by management and accountability. According to this doctrine, mankind is entrusted by God with the responsibility to conserve and safeguard the environment. In Islam, the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the environment is bestowed upon humanity by God. In Islam, the connection between people and their creations is determined by the notions of governance and accountability. According to this ideology, people are seen as custodians entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the environment by a divine entity. In Islam, the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the environment is bestowed upon humanity by God. In Islam, there exists a reciprocal link of obligation and empowerment between people and animals. According to this concept, mankind are stewards entrusted by God the obligation to conserve and safeguard the environment.

Islamic perspective on management and responsibility

In Islam, it is believed that mankind has been entrusted by Allah with the responsibility to safeguard and preserve the environment. This concept highlights the need to safeguard and maintain the

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Earth, since mankind perceives it as a revered endowment and creation. The concept of divine accountability in the hereafter serves as the foundation for individuals' sense of duty towards their surroundings in Islam. In Islam, the connection between people and their creations is determined by the duty of rulership and the obligation to safeguard the world from destruction. The principle of management is deeply ingrained in Islamic culture and values, shown in the conduct of the first Caliph, Abu Bakr. He explicitly directed his commander to refrain from annihilating natural resources and maintain reverence for the environment (Mostafa, 2016). Furthermore, environmental communication has significant importance in the Islamic faith. Humans possess the capacity for verbal communication, and it is important that we use this faculty to acquire knowledge about environmental concerns and disseminate information to others. Islam stresses the important responsibility of humanity as environmental stewards, who are entrusted by God to safeguard and maintain the environment (Ghazali et al., 2018). According to Islamic teachings, humanity have been entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and overseeing the environment. In Islam, the responsibility of safeguarding and preserving the environment is bestowed to humanity by the divine. In Islam, the relationship between mankind and its creations is delineated by the function of the ruler and the related obligations. In Islam, the connection between people and animals is defined by the notions of custody and accountability. In Islam, the ideals of stewardship and responsibility establish the connection between people and animals. In the Islamic faith, humanity is entrusted by God with the responsibility of safeguarding and conserving the environment. In Islam, individuals are obligated to safeguard and preserve the environment. In Islam, the interaction between people and animals entails the principles of stewardship and accountability. This perspective regards people as custodians entrusted with the responsibility of safeguarding and preserving the world under the care and guardianship of God. In Islam, there exists a bond of guardianship and accountability between people and species. In Islam, the connection between people and their creations is characterized by management and accountability. This conviction entrusted humanity with the responsibility to foster and safeguard the environment. In Islam, the connection between people and their creations is characterized by a profound feeling of

accountability. In Islam, there exists a reciprocal link of obligation and empowerment between people and animals. This concept regards people as custodians entrusted with the responsibility of God's supervision and safeguarding of the world. The connection between mankind and the natural world in Islam is determined by the concepts of governance and responsibility. According to this doctrine, people have been entrusted by God with the responsibility to safeguard and preserve the environment. In Islam, there exists a reciprocal link of obligation and empowerment between people and animals. According to this doctrine, mankind is entrusted by God with the responsibility to conserve and safeguard the environment. In the context of Islam, there exists a reciprocal connection of obligation and empowerment between human beings and other living beings. This worldview posits that people are entrusted by God to act as stewards, responsible for safeguarding and nurturing the Earth (Sobaihi, 2019).

Doomsday and Doomsday

1- Some Concepts Related to Doomsday

Doomsday refers to the event of the revival of individuals, whereas sa'ah signifies the occurrence when the established order of the cosmos is disturbed. Those who refrain from falsehood in order to gain access to the presence of Allah are really disadvantaged. When the unforeseen day of reckoning arrives, individuals will lament their neglect of virtuous actions in this earthly realm, burdened by the weight of their transgressions. Take note of the significant weight of the load they bear. "When is its anticipated arrival?" they inquire. "Only my Lord possesses knowledge about him," he said. At the appropriate moment, it is just God who will disclose it. The impending apocalypse will have a profound impact on both the celestial realm and the terrestrial domain. It will seize you abruptly! They inquire as if they had awareness. "The comprehension of it originates from Allah, yet the majority of individuals remain unaware." The word "sa'ah" is used in passages like "Doomsday".

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Doomsday: In the preceding chapters, we examined the genesis of humanity, its contemplation of mortality, and the ultimate outcome of death, leading us to a dire predicament. The doomsday phase begins with the death of an individual and their subsequent interment in a grave. The term "Doomsday" signifies the act of assuming an upright position or standing up. The word "apocalypse" refers to a profound transformation of the world's cosmic system and the eternal revival of the deceased. In the Quran, the term "yewmu'l-kiyamah" refers to the day when Almighty Allah will revive his followers for the purpose of holding them accountable. It is the day when the final hour will occur, and the day of judgment will take place. The phrase "doomsday" refers to the simultaneous occurrence of two events: the change of the current universe system into a new state, and the resurrection of individuals in the afterlife, where they will be held accountable for their actions. It pertains to the specific time at which he will be revived in accordance with a directive.

The term "Azife" refers to the act of continuously moving closer and closer to something. The term "âzife" is one of the titles used to refer to the apocalypse, specifically denoting the imminent arrival of doomsday. In the Holy Quran, the phrase "âzife" signifies that anything that is imminent is not far and may occur unexpectedly. The imminent arrival is now imminent. Allah only possesses assistance. Hakka language: The word "hakka", as used in the Holy Quran, refers to the concept of apocalypse and signifies the undeniable fact of something's existence. "The impending cataclysmic event!" What is the nature of that remarkable occasion? How will you ascertain? The Holy Quran describes this occurrence as an inevitable encounter with the terrifying reality of the apocalypse, stating that no matter how much one may attempt to repress it in their subconscious, they will ultimately be confronted with its horror. "He possesses foresight," he states.

In the Holy Quran, the term "Sahha" refers to a resounding and formidable noise. The apocalyptic event is shown as a trumpet blast accompanied by a deafening voice. The Holy Quran inquires about the consequences that will ensue at the arrival of that dreadful sound. On that day, an individual flees from their sibling, parent, spouse, and offspring. On that particular day, the level of responsibility for each individual is amplified beyond their own scope. During that particular

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day, a multitude of lights emit brightness, exuding a sense of joy and delivering positive tidings. On that day, a multitude of individuals were enveloped in a dark and powdery substance. These individuals are characterized as deniers and sinners. Vâkia is a term that symbolizes the apocalypse, with "vâkia" referring to both past and future events. There is no advantage to disregarding the global catastrophe and avoiding contemplation of it, since that event is inevitable. Once the momentous event occurs, its existence will be irrefutable. It descends and ascends. Karia: "Karia" is another term that describes the dreadful noise that happens with the occurrence of an apocalypse. It refers to the act of an object colliding with another object, resulting in a very audible noise. The Holy Quran mentions the phrase, "That dreadful noise!" What an alarming noise! Are you familiar with the source of that alarming noise?" phrases are included. On that day, individuals scatter in all directions, like the flight pattern of a butterfly. Due to its meaning as the sound of crashing, Kâria is believed to represent the dissolution of the cosmic world during the apocalypse.

When describing the frightening event of the apocalypse, the Holy Quran refers to it as "Tamme". This phrase, denoting "the occurrence of a catastrophic event (doomsday)", serves as an additional statement that characterizes the terror of the apocalypse. In the Holy Quran, the terms "Sayhah", "Racifeh", and "noise" symbolize the apocalypse.

Consequently, the terror and horror associated with the apocalypse are limited to those who do not believe and engage in sinful behavior, as previously said, and have been attempted to be elucidated by extensive verbiage. Those who are obedient and have faith will be spared from experiencing this terror and horror; instead, they will be rewarded with good health and beauty.

2- Doomsday

During the occurrence of the apocalypse, the individuals who are still living will see the event, while those who have already passed away will have been interred in their graves. Death represents

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the end of an individual's existence and the commencement of the subsequent stage after burial. The sounding of the trumpet heralds the beginning of the apocalypse. The sounding of the trumpet heralds the first indication of the beginning of the apocalypse. The Holy Quran declares that when the trumpet is sounded, the bonds of kinship will have no significance, and individuals will be unable to communicate with one another. According to the Holy Quran, the Day of Judgment would be marked by the occurrence of the trumpet blowing event and several unusual phenomena.³⁸³ The trumpet blowing event will occur twice.

The first event will occur at the conclusion of the day, while the second event will take place at the time of resurrection, when individuals will be revived from their burial sites. There is a contentious discussion on the mechanics of trumpet playing. There are several explanations for the origin of the term "blow." others suggest that it refers to a sound, others argue that it is derived from the speed at which the action occurs, and others propose that it is related to the act of blowing a horn. Certain academics have said that it is inappropriate to inquire on the veracity of the wall.

According to the Quran, the apocalypse will occur abruptly. Allah has dominion over the celestial and terrestrial realms. The duration of Doomsday will be very brief, lasting no longer than the duration of a blink or even less. Undoubtedly, Allah has omnipotence. According to reports, the event is expected to occur abruptly, like the rapid illumination of lightning or the swift closing and opening of an eye. Furthermore, it is believed that it would instantaneously seize the future. Those who are honest in their approach to entering God's presence are really disadvantaged. At the moment of swift judgment, they will lament, burdened with their misdeeds, exclaiming: "Alas, we regret forsaking virtuous actions in this earthly realm! Exercise caution since the weight of the load they carry is substantial! Hence, an individual may abruptly manifest upon being entangled and disoriented in the chaotic realm of existence, or they may abruptly manifest as if just a little interval has transpired while they are buried in the grave.

The apocalypse will manifest with a resounding and terrifying noise, generating immense pressure.

Based on the phrases, it is evident that the apocalypse triggered by the blowing of the trumpet will be very brief, lasting no longer than the duration of a blink, and will come abruptly.

3-The Effect of Doomsday on the Universe

During the apocalypse, the whole of the cosmos, including the earth, heavens, mountains, stars, moon, sun, and all other celestial bodies, will cease to exist, marking the beginning of the afterlife. The Holy Quran elucidates the impact of the apocalypse on the cosmos in the following manner. In the future, the planet will undergo a meaningful change, as will the heavens. At that time, individuals will see the appearance of a supreme deity with an indomitable strength. The celestial and terrestrial realms will undergo a radical transformation. While this passage acknowledges that the existing state of the heavens and the earth will undergo transformation, it emphasizes that this transition is not intended for annihilation, but rather to provide the necessary circumstances for the emergence of new life. Additional passages suggest the potential for altering the heavens and the earth. During a significant seismic event, the earth experiences a powerful earthquake, causing the mountains to disintegrate into fine particles and emit smoke. Upon the sounding of the trumpet, the earth and mountains shall be dislodged and collide, signifying the arrival of that momentous day. On that day, the order of things crumbled as the sky was torn asunder. Await the day when the atmosphere will be engulfed in noxious fumes, enveloping all individuals. This is excruciating agony. According to the Scriptures, the world will tremble when the trumpet is sounded. The typically serene and unclouded sky will be violently torn apart. The mountains, regarded as the foundational supports of the planet, will disintegrate into fine particles and airborne emissions. The mountains are questioned. "My Lord will dismantle them and disperse them." He will vacate their positions. The depiction of the mountains and the earth at the catastrophic time of the apocalypse was portrayed via numerous means. When the mountains shift, they transform into mirages. The mountains undergo a transformation, assuming vibrant hues

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reminiscent of wool. During that day, there will be seismic activity as both the mountains and the ground experience tremors. The mountains will crumble and transform into heaps of fine sand. As the mountains erode, the soil will likewise dissolve, leading to a disruption of the natural order. The text depicts the alarming state of not just the Earth, but also the Sun, animals, and oceans on that particular day. An individual will acquire knowledge of their actions during the occurrence of celestial events such as the sun being rolled up and darkened, the falling and extinguishing of stars, the dismantling and relocation of mountains, the neglect of camels giving birth, the gathering of wild animals, and the boiling of oceans. Another passage affirms that the stars, including the sun, descend and extinguish. Additionally, it might signify the eradication of a species. Hence, the act of rolling up and obscuring the sun signifies the cessation of its illumination. Upon closer examination of the mountainous terrain, it becomes evident that even the most formidable fortresses in the globe would be reduced to ruins under the cataclysmic devastation of the apocalypse. Neglecting pregnant camels results in the devaluation of a significant aspect of Arab culture. It signifies the act of forsaking even significant matters.

This chapter demonstrates the profound impact of the apocalypse on the earth, mountains, sun, stars, and animals. This picture depicts a cataclysmic revolution that completely upends the established order. Human people naturally get pleasure and a sense of calm from familiar experiences, whereas change and uncertainty evoke fear and unease. People are frightened by such a transformation.

He relinquishes even the most precious possessions, and assets undergo unforeseen transformations.

Furthermore, "During a lunar eclipse, when the moon is obscured and the sun and moon align;" Put simply, the month will also undergo a shift. As previously said, this process will upset the cosmic order and cause all entities to undergo changes.

4-The Effects of the Apocalypse on People

The universe serves to inform individuals about this catastrophic occurrence and serve as a reminder of its inevitable occurrence. This unprecedented occurrence promises universal information dissemination, leading to heightened awareness among individuals. The Quran depicts the apocalypse as a cataclysmic and awe-inspiring occurrence. While the task may provide challenges for those whom Allah chooses, it is easy for those who lack faith. When the trumpet is sounded, all beings in the heavens and the earth will submit to Him with their heads down, save those whom Allah chooses not to. The portrayal of the Doomsday evokes a sense of terror and presents formidable problems that test the limits of human imagination. Dear individuals! It is advisable to refrain from defying your deity. The occurrence of a catastrophic earthquake is an immensely significant event. When you encounter him, all lactating women will lose memory of the kid they have breastfed, and all expectant women will terminate the pregnancy they are carrying. And many will look inebriated, while they are not drunk; for Allah's punishment (the horror of the apocalypse) is extremely terrible."

The bond of love and compassion shared between a mother and child is the most profound and kind form of love in existence.

Doomsday will be a catastrophic event that may cause a mother to neglect breastfeeding her kid and a pregnant woman to have a miscarriage due to extreme worry. Mothers often depart and care for their offspring. Individuals will aimlessly roam while intoxicated, overwhelmed by the terror of the apocalypse.

"When their eyeballs protrude", "when they are overwhelmed by brightness and sudden bursts of

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light", "Forewarn them of the approaching day, as their hearts will be filled with fear, and they will gulp in panic; the oppressors will have no ally or mediator who will not be heeded. The Quran elucidates the state of the disbelievers at the time of reckoning and delineates their impending fate. Simultaneously, individuals will experience astonishment and confusion over their actions. On that day, individuals will scatter in a manner reminiscent to butterflies. The word "dispersion" refers to the phenomenon where individuals who are unsure of their destination may disperse in many directions.

Elsewhere, he said that individuals lost consciousness and proclaimed, "On that particular day, the trumpet shall resound, causing all beings in the celestial and terrestrial realms to collapse and lose consciousness, with the exception of those whom Allah deems worthy. Subsequently, the trumpet shall resound once more, prompting them to rise and survey their surroundings." As previously said, "ten months pregnant" The proverb "the camels will be released" symbolizes the abandonment of one's most cherished possessions and the fleeing from loved ones, including family members, at the Day of Judgment. On that day, everyone's obligation is larger than their own. On that particular day, several lights emit brightness; They exude a sense of joy and positive tidings.

On that day, a multitude of individuals were enveloped in darkness and debris. These individuals are characterized as deniers and sinners. Sayyid Qutb asserts that the anxiety shown in this scenario is a psychological fear that isolates the individual from their family members, leaving them alone. Amidst this worry, individuals are preoccupied with their own concerns. Currently, each person is independently grappling with their own issue and is not obligated to consider the well-being of others. Put simply, the individual's predicament is of such magnitude that it might lead to a complete estrangement from their closest companions. He refrains from interrogating his friend's circumstances. Nevertheless, they are shown to one another. To alleviate the anguish he experienced on that particular day, an individual burdened with guilt offers his sons, wife, brothers, extended family who provide him with protection, and every individual in the whole globe as recompense. These phrases indicate that individuals will experience intense fear and terror on the

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Day of Judgment, resulting in the breakdown and malfunction of everything.

The depiction of mankind's terror and horror towards the catastrophe is shown with exceptional clarity and intensity, beyond the bounds of imagination.

STAGES OF THE AFTERLIFE

1-Hashr

The term "Hashr" can be found in the dictionary, and it is defined as the act of forcibly assembling a community in a square. The phrase "resurrection" refers to the gathering of creatures on the Day of Judgment in a square for the purpose of being evaluated.

Upon examining the passages in the Holy Quran pertaining to this tragedy, the primary focus is on the veracity of this event. Hz. All individuals who have existed throughout history, starting from the time of Adam, shall be assembled simultaneously, and summoned for judgment at an undisclosed moment known only to God.

Oh, Almighty God! You will undoubtedly assemble the individuals on a day that is unquestionably certain. Allah's commitment is unwavering, and He will never fail to fulfill His promises. On the Day of Judgment, your Lord will gather them. He has a wealth of information and demonstrates wisdom. The only opportunity for repose on that particular day is in the proximity of your divine Master. According to the Holy Quran, individuals shall be deprived of their attributes and brought together as humble slaves. In the hereafter, all the attributes that one has inherited or acquired in this world, including as social status, occupation, gender, ethnicity, and so on, will have no significance. Instead, all individuals will be assembled in the sight of Allah on an equal footing. "All individuals in the celestial and terrestrial realms will serve the Most Merciful, without any exclusions." Both the Messiah and the angels in His proximity will steadfastly remain as devoted

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servants of Allah. Allah will shortly assemble all those who display arrogance and abstain from worshipping Him in His presence. Another portrayal of the Day of Judgment has individuals arranged in rows, with no one possessing any kind of dominance over another. "Now they will all be assembled before their Lord in orderly formations: 'Indeed, you have returned to us just as We originally made you.' Nevertheless, you believed that we had not designated a certain time for our meeting with you.

During the occurrence of the apocalypse, as previously said, the ground will rupture, individuals will promptly emerge from their graves, they will swiftly converge towards the summoner, and they will assemble harmoniously. However, at the day of reckoning, some individuals will encounter adversity while others will experience contentment and serenity. Put simply, individuals who are concerned about the end of the world and structure their lives accordingly will be assembled in the presence of God with radiant and jubilant expressions, akin to esteemed ambassadors and guests. Conversely, those who are unbelievers, oppressors, and those who reject the teachings of the Quran will experience a change in eye color due to fear, and subsequently become visually impaired, deaf, and unable to speak. They will assemble with expressions of sorrow and discontent, their countenances engulfed in flames.

The Holy Quran prioritizes the recognition and understanding of the resurrection rather than providing intricate details about it. Narrative sources provide the majority of specific information. Upon examining the narrations, it becomes evident that the location of judgment is a level terrain. It is depicted as a region devoid of any distinguishing landmarks, resembling a smooth and unblemished surface, akin to the whiteness and flatness of refined flour. The apocalypse is characterized by the following scenario: During Hashr, individuals will be devoid of footwear and clothing, and will be engulfed by the masses and intense heat. The contemporary human intellect will have challenges in comprehending the location where people would assemble during the apocalypse. During the moment of Judgment, individuals will be utterly powerless in the presence of Allah's omnipotent nature.

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Individuals will experience a new realm as their autonomy has been deprived from them. "In the future, the earth will undergo a profound transformation, resulting in a different environment, while the skies will also undergo a significant change. During this transformation, individuals will encounter the supreme deity, whose power is invincible." "Those whom Allah guides are the ones who discover the correct path, and those whom He diverts from the correct path will not have any advocates except Allah." On the Day of Judgment, we shall assemble them in a state of blindness, muteness, and deafness, compelling them to go forward on their faces. Their ultimate destination is hell. As the intensity of its fire diminishes, we prolong their suffering by intensifying the flames of their misery. These terms indicate that the resurrection will be arduous, formidable, and challenging. In a separate set of verses, the interaction between Allah and a transgressor is conveyed in the following manner: "Anyone who disregards My remembrance will undoubtedly experience a life filled with difficulties, and on the Day of Judgment, we will resurrect them blind." The individual expresses: "Oh my Lord!" Why did you revive me without the ability to see? Nevertheless, I was an individual who saw it before. According to Allah, the matter is concluded. Upon receiving Our verses, you have neglected them, and now you too have been disregarded in a same manner! These words convey that God, in portraying the day of judgment, both cautions and reveals that this is the manner in which He would penalize those who disregard Him on that day. The passage above describes the concept of being resurrected without the ability to see, hear, or speak, and also highlights the subject matter discussed in this particular verse. Some individuals saw the discourse as conflicting.

Nevertheless, it has been said that this matter is connected to the several phases of the apocalypse, beginning with the revival and rebirth.

Several Islamic scholars have asserted that the concept of resurrection would pertain to the spiritual realm rather than the physical one. According to the Holy Quran, as previously said, it asserts that the soul and body shall be joined together and thereafter recognized.

2-Account

This stage has great significance since it contains the highest number of verses dedicated to it, unveiling the fundamental principles of existence in both the present world and the hereafter. The purpose of our existence in this world and the subsequent phases of recuperation after death are the subjects of discussion.

According to the Holy Quran, God created death and life in order to assess and determine whether individuals exhibit superior conduct. He has great physical strength and demonstrates a willingness to pardon others. He asserts that Allah will assess the actions and hold individuals responsible for them. Following the Day of Resurrection, individuals will be summoned to the divine presence of Allah. The reckoning will promptly commence, and all individuals will be brought into the presence of Allah to account for their actions. Transgressors will be questioned about their actions and the motivations behind them. Allah has omniscience over the actions of his followers. Therefore, Allah has appointed Himself as a witness to His actions towards humanity on the Day of Judgment. On the Day of Judgment, Allah will exercise authority over those who have faith, those who have converted to Judaism, Sabians, Christians, Magians, and those who have engaged in polytheism. Undoubtedly, Allah is an omniscient witness to all things. The Qur'an addresses the concept of the reckoning period. The Holy Quran states, "Had Allah desired, He could have unified all of you into a single community of faith." Nevertheless, He grants permission to whoever He desires and directs whomever He desires towards the correct path.

You may face interrogation due to your recent activities. We will undoubtedly interrogate every one of them for their actions! Furthermore, apart from the passages mandating the occurrence of the accounting phase, it is Allah who will ultimately determine all the outcomes. During that particular day, all individuals will maintain a state of silence, with the exception of Allah and those

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individuals whom He grants permission to communicate. It is impossible for anybody to conceal anything within. During that particular day, all individuals will unquestioningly comply with the person summoning them; evading this obligation is unattainable. The voices are suppressed by the grandeur of the Most Merciful; now only weak noises can be perceived. During a time when both the soul and angels are in a state of purity, only those who have been granted compassion will be rendered speechless. Furthermore, anybody who does speak will be compelled to proclaim the truth. According to the Holy Quran, individual accountability is emphasized, stating that each person is responsible for their own faults and cannot be held accountable for the sins of others. During the accounting phase, individuals will be held accountable for their own acts and behaviors. In the absence of the kind of uncertainty that exists in the world, no one would experience oppression in that place.

There will be a time when individuals are unable to provide financial assistance to others, and no one can intervene or substitute on their behalf, resulting in a lack of support. "While you will not be held accountable for the offenses we perpetrated, we shall likewise not assume responsibility for your conduct," he said. During the calculation stage, nothing that has significance or worth in this world possesses any value or worth in that context. It is futile. An individual's convictions and actions will be attributed solely to them and will be subject to scrutiny appropriately.

Indubitably, you must individually return to us, in the same manner that we first fashioned you, and you will relinquish all we have bestowed upon you. Furthermore, we will not have the opportunity to see your intermediaries who you regard as your associates. There seems to be a significant disagreement between you and your previous belief in a divine being. Each benefit has a corresponding obligation in this world and will therefore be subject to scrutiny. As previously said, God has bestowed upon humanity several benefits, including intellect, will, and sentiment. He claims responsibility for this. On that particular day, undoubtedly, you will be interrogated on the favors bestowed upon you. As previously said, Allah has appointed him as a witness in the celestial tribunal that will occur on the Day of Judgment.

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Nevertheless, it is said that both divine testimony and individual testimony may serve as self-witnesses.

We assumed accountabilities for all individuals. During the Day of Judgment, we shall present an unsealed book in front of all individuals. Commence reading your book now! Today, it is necessary for you to rely on your own judgment to evaluate yourself. "On that day, mankind will be apprised of all their actions, both committed and omitted." Regardless of the many reasons he may use, mankind is today an observer of its own actions. During the day of reckoning, the individual will provide testimony using all of their bodily organs instead of relying just on their tongue. Specifically, organs like as the tongue, hands, feet, and skin will communicate and testify to the crimes committed using them, with the consent of Allah. The body book serves as a testament to the organs, which meticulously document every action performed by an individual. On that day, we shall silence their speech; their actions and movements will serve as evidence. During the day of reckoning, individuals and societies will face interrogation, with the prophets serving as witnesses for each society. On that day, we will choose a representative from each country to testify, and we will appoint you as a witness against them. This book has been bestowed upon people who are really dedicated to Allah, and it serves as a comprehensive source of instruction, direction, and compassion in all aspects. We will summon a representative from each country and request, "Present your conclusive evidence!" We must express. Subsequently, they comprehended that the ultimate veracity is with Allah, prompting them to abandon the worship of idols. Another characteristic of the accounting stage is that it does not function as a judicial entity, unlike in the physical realm. The accounting process is executed expeditiously. With the arrival of many individuals on Earth, the process of reckoning will occur promptly, resembling the accountability of a solitary person. There will be no delay for anybody, since each individual will just see the reckoning of another person, experiencing a sense of being summoned for judgment.

3-Trial balance

In theological parlance, balance refers to the act of assessing, approximating, or quantifying the magnitude of something. The assessment of actions that warrant punishment or reward is necessary to conclude the interrogation of taxpayers during a certain phase of the hereafter, based on the severity of their acts.

Mizan embodies the concept of fairness and impartiality. The purpose is to underline that justice will remain unchanged on the day of judgment. According to divine communication, individuals were informed that their acts of virtue and transgressions would be evaluated, akin to the use of scales to impartially determine excess and deficiency.

The accounting phase encompasses the trial balance phase. Once the individuals have assembled, they will be presented before the divine being. He, his organs, and the prophets shall bear testimony to the virtuous or malevolent actions performed by individuals. Once the sins and rewards have been recounted, a thorough evaluation of both the virtuous and wicked actions will take place, particularly in terms of their significance and impact. On the Day of Judgment, we shall establish the scales of justice, ensuring that no one will be subjected to unjust treatment.

We disclose our actions, regardless of their insignificance, even if they are as minute as a mustard seed. We possess exceptional abilities as calculators. This is the most compelling evidence that Allah exists and is real in the sceneries of the hereafter. This underscores the fact that the equilibrium is genuine and accurate.

others with elevated scales may effortlessly reunite with their loved ones with a simple calculation, whilst others with diminished scales would experience distress and encounter arduous computations. On that day, the measurement and weight will be accurate. The individuals with a greater weight on their scales will be the ones that are rescued. The one who has a greater magnitude of virtuous actions will have a life filled with contentment and joy. On that day, the absolute

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authority of the Merciful shall manifest, causing great hardship for those who do not believe. The individual with the greater magnitude of scales will be rescued.

Individuals who squander their potential receive a little income. They will endure eternal damnation.

The flames will directly impact their faces, causing their lips to contort and their teeth to become revealed. The last step of God's salvation is the decisive moment when a choice must be made after carefully evaluating one's actions. In the preceding sections, we have said that if Allah bestows His favor upon an individual whom He holds dear, and if that person is unable to attain the desired status via their actions, Allah subjects them to hardship as a means of guiding them towards that position.

According to the Holy Quran, Allah has the authority to forgive the sins of anybody He chooses. Even if their actions are insufficient for them to reach paradise, Allah will still show them kindness and conceal their transgressions. Nevertheless, it is explicitly mentioned that this is not intended for amusement and the individual in question will personally choose the definitive position. "Those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions for both the present life and the afterlife, we will indeed eliminate their past wrongdoings and compensate them with the finest recompense for their deeds." Associating partners with Allah is an egregious offense and an act of defamation that Allah never forgives. Engaging in a grave transgression is a further factor that prompts Allah to exercise forgiveness and exercise discernment prior to rendering a verdict. Allah will pardon the slaves who abstain from committing little crimes, as He Himself refrains from doing great sins. The individual is said to be willing to acknowledge and pardon their small transgressions. Furthermore, the individual's purpose, which holds primary accountability for their actions, will significantly influence decision-making throughout the judgment process.

4-Amel Book

According to the Holy Quran, there is a book that records all information about an individual throughout the process of evaluation, and it will be examined once the final outcome is determined. Similar to the divine, celestial beings, and bodily systems, the records of individuals' actions, known as books of deeds, will serve as evidence of their conduct. The guardian angels compile these notebooks, which are subsequently unsealed and examined on the day of judgment. They include a record of each individual's assigned responsibilities. During the Day of Judgment, we shall provide an unveiled book to the people. Every community will prostrate and submit.

Each community will be designated by its respective book, and on that specific day, you will get a prize based on your actions. This is our publication that reveals factual information, documenting all of your actions. The Holy Quran refers to the books of deeds as "books" and describes them as meticulously recording all actions performed in the earth. These books will be submitted as proof to individuals. The sequential arrangement of the content, starting with the simplest and progressing to the most significant, not only signifies the magnitude of the impending judgment but also serves as a testament to the fairness of God's justice. The Book of Deeds has now been unveiled, causing fear among the offenders who, upon reading its contents, will exclaim, "Alas for us! This book is very remarkable! They will state, "He has meticulously listed all of them, without omitting anything, whether it is insignificant or significant." Consequently, they realized that their actions were evident before them. We understand that the Lord is equitable and does not show injustice against anybody. The Holy Quran explicitly references the titles of these books and affirms that the writings pertaining to righteousness and wickedness would be distinct from one another. The notebook belonging to those with malevolent intentions is referred to as "siccin," whereas the notebook belonging to individuals with virtuous intentions is referred to as "illiyyin."

Absolutely not! Undoubtedly, the history of ethical individuals is ancient. Are you familiar with the concept of Illiyyin? The actions and observations of persons who have a strong connection with

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Allah are documented. Consequently, the criminal's writing is unquestionably documented in their record. Are you familiar with the concept of Sijjin? These actions represent a document. In addition, individuals will get their deed books on both their right and left sides. Individuals receiving from the left side will experience sadness and sorrow, while those receiving from the right side will feel pleasure and happiness. The individual who appropriated the book from the right-hand side remarked, "Take and peruse my literary work; indeed, I was already cognizant of the impending consequences I would face." He began to have a prosperous life. Evidently, there are virtuous individuals in the world. Individuals that engage in virtuous actions will encounter tranquility and joy, whilst those who do wrongdoings will suffer agitation and discontentment.

5-A'raf

A'raf refers to the apex or pinnacle of a structure, such as a wall, rampart, or curtain. A'raf is a term used in the Holy Quran to describe the uppermost section of the wall that separates heaven and hell. The Surah Al-A'raf, which is referenced in just two verses of the Holy Quran, has been the topic of several disputes.

There is a barrier between the two sides, and in Purgatory, there are individuals who can recognize everyone by their facial features. They greet the people from heaven, whom they want to join, with the words "Peace be upon you!" even if they too have not yet reached heaven. Upon their return to the inhabitants of Hell, they will beseech, "O our Lord! Do not associate ourselves with those who engage in wrongful behavior! The inhabitants of Araf confronted some individuals whom they recognized by their appearances and said, "The authority you have amassed and the haughtiness you have adopted have proven to be futile." The passages indicate that the inhabitants of Araf greeted those who aspired to join paradise, despite their inability to do so. Upon seeing the inhabitants of hell, they beseeched God to remove them from that place. He expressed his intention

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to fervently pray in order to avoid being associated with the oppressors.

Islamic scholars acknowledge that the individuals residing in A'raf are those whose transgressions and merits are of equal measure. While the Holy Quran mentions that paradise or hell awaits based on the weight of one's works, it does not provide clarification on the outcome if the deeds are of equal measure. The scripture implies that even if the inhabitants of A'raf have a strong longing for heaven, they will not be able to enter there. Upon seeing this, he implores the divine intervention of God. Consequently, the crimes and rewards of the inhabitants of A'raf are identical. This is derived from this perspective.

The inhabitants of A'raf will exchange greetings and compliments while simultaneously expressing disapproval towards the people of Hell.

Consequently, it is anticipated to originate from prophets or angels.

6. The consequences of actions in the hereafter are shown as paradise for those who behave virtuously and as hell for those who are wicked and defiant. As to the Quran, this conclusion is unavoidable and will bring delight to some individuals. Due to the endowment of reason and free will by Allah, individuals will be rewarded or punished based on their deliberate decisions and actions. Individuals experience prompt consequences, whether positive or negative, as a result of their activities in the world. Texts on the topic include menacing declarations, admonitions, positive tidings, and solace.

On the day of reckoning, when individuals will confront the good acts, they have accomplished and the bad crimes they have perpetrated, humans will want a significant separation between themselves and their malevolent actions. You are being cautioned by God about his own nature. Allah demonstrates immense benevolence towards His worshippers. "Anyone who performs even the most minimal act of benevolence will receive its corresponding recompense." Furthermore, those who engage in malevolent actions will inevitably face the consequences of their deeds.

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Following the process of calculation and evaluation, individuals will peruse the book, leading to a determination. Consequently, some individuals will exhibit expressions of delight, whilst others will display countenances of despondency. Upon receiving good news, the countenance of the recipient will display a grin, however upon learning of an unfavorable destiny, the countenance of the individual would exhibit tears. Upon the announcement of the decision, the true emotions and expressions of individuals will be exposed.

On that particular day, a multitude of lights radiate, exuding a joyful countenance as they bask in the reception of positive tidings. On that particular day, several countenances were obscured by a layer of soot and grime. These individuals are nonbelievers and transgressors. In the future, there will be a significant increase in both light-skinned and dark-skinned individuals. Those whose countenances have grown obscured will be addressed, "Have you renounced your faith after embracing it?" Therefore, experience the anguish as a consequence of your disbelief! According to widespread belief. Those individuals whose faces will be pale will stay in the eternal grace of Allah. The Holy Quran provides explanations for why humans experience these emotions. Generally, mankind become the people of fire due to their forgetfulness of the day of judgment. Typically, faith and good acts serve as the basis for individuals to attain paradise.

Oh David! You have been appointed as the caliph on earth. It is imperative that you govern with fairness and impartiality. Refrain from succumbing to the temptations of your own wants, as they may divert you from the righteous path set by Allah. Without a doubt, those who deviate from the path of Allah will experience severe punishment due to their disregard for the day of judgment. Fortunate are individuals who have faith and engage in virtuous actions, benefiting both the present life and the hereafter! They will visit a picturesque destination. The concepts of heaven and hell are often encountered by individuals in the hereafter. The Holy Quran provides a comprehensive depiction of the many tiers, statuses, and appellations associated with both heaven and hell. This name is sometimes given based on the nature of the suffering or favor, and at other times based on the specific manifestation of the suffering or favor.

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Seats of Heaven

1—Heaven: Heaven is the term used to refer to the realm of eternal pleasure in the afterlife, where all the gifts and rewards shall be bestowed onto their rightful recipients. In the Holy Quran, the term "hell" denotes several locations and states, serving as the antithesis of "heaven".

The Holy Quran not only use the term "heaven," but also provides a detailed description of its nature and characteristics. Those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions for both the present life and the hereafter will be granted entry into paradises with flowing rivers underneath them. They will have loyal friends and we will position them in a dense shadow.

2- Cennetü'n-Naîm : Naim is a term that signifies a state of tranquility and contentment. Prosperity encompasses both financial and spiritual aspects that provide happiness to individuals. The term "Cennetü'n-Naim" appears in 10 instances throughout the Holy Quran. The term signifies an abundance of joy in the celestial realm. Furthermore, the fundamental prerequisites for gaining entry into these celestial realms are faith, virtuous actions, and abstaining from defying the commands of Allah.

Their Lord provides guidance to people who have faith and engage in virtuous actions, both in this life and the hereafter. Beneath the ground, rivers run, nourishing gardens that abound with benefits. Those who refuse to comply with Allah's commands will be rewarded with abundant rewards from their Lord in the form of heavenly realms. Those who fail to show reverence towards Allah will find contentment in the bounties bestowed upon them by their divine Master and will reside in a state of bliss inside paradise. Furthermore, their divine Master will shield them from the agonizing punishment of the inferno.

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3- Name : The term "Adn" is often understood to refer to the celestial realm. The term "heaven" is repeated in 10 places throughout the Holy Quran, with its characteristics being explicitly described. Within the idyllic realm of Eden, an abundance of gifts awaits to bestow delight upon its inhabitants. These include flowing rivers, opulent palaces, succulent fruits, refreshing beverages, and exquisite garments. Furthermore, those who visit that place will be exposed to encouraging messages, and a wide range of joyous experiences will be bestowed upon the virtuous devotees.

However, this does not apply to those who express remorse, have faith, and engage in virtuous actions. The servants of Allah, the Most Merciful, will get access to the paradise of Eden, a realm that beyond human comprehension. His assurance will certainly be fulfilled. They shall have eternal existence in the paradisiacal gardens of Eden, with flowing rivers underneath! This is the recompense bestowed to people who have been delivered from transgressions.

4- Firdevs: The name Firdevs signifies a vineyard abundant with grapes. The Holy Quran affirms that those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions will congregate in this place, which is both everlasting and compelling, and will have no desire to go from there.

Those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions will reside eternally in the paradise of Firdevs, both in this world and the hereafter. They are unwilling to go from that location. "Those who have faith have undoubtedly attained salvation; they will inherit the Paradise of Firdevs and will dwell there eternally."

5- Dâru's - Selam: It is referred to as a designation and characteristic of paradise, denoting "a place of tranquility".

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It is referred to be a heavenly realm where individuals who are spared from suffering will be granted entry, due to the benevolence of Allah, and where many forms of delights are found.

The dwelling of peace with their Lord is reserved for them. Allah becomes their ally due to their virtuous actions. Allah invites individuals to a state of tranquility and directs those whom He chooses towards the correct course of action.

6-Dâru'l-Mukâme: ' The term 'mukame', which translates to 'a perpetual dwelling, a country without an exit', signifies the everlasting nature of all the heavenly gifts.

"By His benevolence, He has situated us in the eternal dwelling." There, we shall experience neither fatigue nor ennui."

7- Daru'l-Ahire: The phrase is defined as "the ultimate destination, the permanent abode." The country that awaits the devout and believers is known as the hereafter, where those who choose to believe and execute their duty towards Allah will be rewarded, even if they endure various hardships in this world. The existence of this planet is really a kind of amusement and diversion. Undoubtedly, the dwelling place of the hereafter is superior for the righteous. Do you continue to lack comprehension? Once again, the many designations for heaven and their distinct compositions are elucidated using terms like as 'secure posture', which conveys the notion of being dependable. In broad words, it is said that paradise is devoid of any worries or unhappiness and is only characterized by bliss and tranquility.

Heaven as a Place of Reward

The Holy Quran provides a concise description of paradise, stating that it would be devoid of dread or sadness. It also emphasizes the absence of fatigue, monotony, and weariness, as well as the absence of empty words or falsehoods. There will alone exist a state of optimal health and contentment. Upon arrival in paradise, individuals will be warmly welcomed and acknowledged with utmost reverence. Furthermore, the portrayal effectively conveys the notion that paradise encompasses an array of unimaginable gifts and all things that provide joy to individuals. Regarding the benefits of heaven, it is said that there will be a wide array of delectable food and beverages that cater to human preferences. "We provide them with ample quantities of the fruit and meat they crave." According to the description, heaven would have vineyards and gardens, abundant with many types of fruit-bearing trees. The inhabitants of heaven will have unlimited access to all the fruits they want.

Once again, the Qur'an often used the metaphor of rivers running under certain locations when depicting paradise. God has created for them eternal abodes adorned with lush gardens and flowing rivers. This is immense joy. Furthermore, it is said that celestial realms are adorned with rivers of imperishable water, rivers of unchanging milk, rivers of purified honey, and rivers of wine that bestow delightful taste onto those who partake. They will recline and indulge in the comfort of beds, pillows, mattresses, and armchairs while savoring delectable cuisine and beverages. They are resting against vibrant, exquisitely attractive cushions.(They will be instructed:) "Indulge in the consumption of food and beverages, while comfortably reclining on arranged seating, as a recompense for your actions." "Additionally, we will unite them in matrimony with wives possessing captivating eyes." Additionally, it is said that there will be attendants and celestial maidens, who will serve as an additional source of bliss. "Their youthful attendants, resembling concealed pearls within their iridescent shells, orbit around them." "We will also bring them together with spouses who have fair skin and large, innocent-looking eyes." "Those who have a fear of defying Allah find themselves in a secure and protected position. They reside in the celestial

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realm and have access to abundant water sources. They are in the company of their loved ones, adorned in luxurious silk and brocade garments." "They will have everlasting gardens with flowing rivers beneath them," In that place, they will be dressed in green robes made of high-quality and dense silk. Additionally, they will be decked with gold bracelets. Moreover, they will be seated on thrones, signifying their position and authority. What an exquisite prize, what an exquisite house! "Those who have faith and engage in virtuous actions, both in this life and the afterlife, shall be granted entry into a splendid paradise." The Holy Quran has several passages that describe heaven. However, in this context, we want to provide a broad explanation of heaven to enhance our understanding of the topic. In general, it is often said that all things that provide joy and delight to individuals are found in paradise, where people will experience a wide range of gifts and pleasures, leading to a state of perpetual bliss.

Layers of Hell

1-Hell : The term "hell" is utilized first while discussing the depths of hell. According to the Sunnah, Hell is described as the uppermost and most intense level of punishment, where sinful believers would be sent after completing their sentence. The concept of undergoing a certain duration of punishment in hell and thereafter being liberated is a subject of much debate. Generally, hell may be defined as the designation for the whole punishment in the hereafter, with its highest level being the topmost layer. "We admonished him, urging him to revere Allah!" Should he affirm it, his arrogance would compel him to transgress. He deserves to be in hell! What a malevolent bed that is!

2- Cahîm : The term "cahim" refers to an intense and layered fire, often seen in a pit, which symbolizes ongoing suffering. The intensity of this fire is formidable, emitting audible sounds as

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it burns. The auditory perception of the intense combustion noise emitted by this fire is likewise seen as a kind of anguish. Individuals will experience fear in response to this fire, to the extent that even the sound of their own breath will undergo alteration.

3- Haviye: Haviye refers to a location characterized by a substantial and expansive cavity, often resulting from a fall. While the term "haviye" is used in the Holy Quran as the pit of hell, it is also described as a blazing inferno with intense heat. "Haviye is the entity that will fully accept and support it." Are you familiar with its identity? An intense blaze!

4- Hutame : The term "Hutame" is used throughout the Holy Quran to convey the notions of breaking, crumbling, and destroying. It is specifically used to describe how Allah's ignited fire ascends to the hearts. "Negative!" I guarantee that he will be sent into the hutame. Are you familiar with the term "hutame"? The divine flame ignited! The flames engulfing them, as they are bound to elongated stakes, ascend, and encircle their hearts!

5- Lezâ : Lezâ, derived from Arabic, is a term used in the Holy Quran to describe a phenomenon of intense heat that causes the skin to peel off and burn.

"However, the realm of possibilities is vast!" It is important to understand that hell is a fiery inferno that burns and causes the flesh to peel.

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6- Sair: "Sair," a term used in the Holy Quran, refers to the act of igniting the fire and also signifies the dynamic and enduring nature of the flames. Those who oppress have been cursed by Allah and will face a scorching fire as punishment. "When the inferno of hell is kindled;"

7- Sakar: In the Holy Quran, the term "sakar" refers to a destructive force that burns and consumes anything, leaving nothing behind. It also has the ability to sear people's flesh. Essentially, "sakar" signifies a violent and intense kind of burning.

I intend to condemn him to eternal damnation in the fiery depths of hell. Sekar is a term that refers to a certain concept or entity. Can you provide further context or details on what you are referring to? The situation concludes, although it forbids annihilation; it inflicts harm upon individuals.

Hell as Punishment

The Holy Quran describes hell as a conflagration. The punishments inflicted upon them consistently involve fire and intense heat. The fire was manifested through the positioning of individuals and their garments. "We admonished him, urging him to have reverence for Allah. If he says so, his pride will drive him to transgress.

He deserves to be in hell! The bed is pretty awful! The two of them are two sides battling for their Lord. Among them, the unbelieving donned garments of fire and hot water was poured on their heads. Along with the bed and clothes of fire, one of the difficulties of hell is having boiling water poured on their heads.

The Holy Quran declares that sinners may be detected by their cheeks, forelocks, and feet. Rings are fastened around their necks, and they are chained in turn.

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They will be taken into the heart of hell with shackles and people. As they approach the flames, they will get exceedingly thirsty. They will be compelled to drink enough hot water to scorch their cheeks and shred their guts to bits, and then they will stay in the fire.

There he will be made to drink pus as another punishment. (The horny) will not drink anything that quenches their thirst in hell. However, they taste boiling water and pus in accordance with what they did in the world . Boiling water is given to them to protect them from the heat caused by the fire in hell. Additionally, it removes pus, pus, sweat, a dirty, moist, and sticky taste from the skin and eyes. There is also a hot and fiery wind that is described as a scorching torment.

Sinners are also given oleander food. Food that is disgusting in hell or the food of the people of hell is called oleander. You will definitely eat from the oleander tree. You will fill your bellies with it. You will also drink that boiling water. Also, thirsty camels are not fooled by drinking water. This will welcome them on the day of judgment! It looks like there will be great fear and pain in hell. Sinners will be in such a tricky situation that they will want to die or disappear, but death will not come, and the torment will be permanent. In general, hell has been described as a terrible, terrible place where people will be unhappy and suffering.

CONCLUSION

Humans were designed to be superior. Typically, it comprises both the physical body and the immaterial soul. Aside from the physical and spiritual aspects that constitute a human person, their cognitive faculties, consciousness, cognitive processes, volition, affective states, and other mental activities enable them to engage in interactions with other entities. Possessing these capabilities enables an individual to surmount certain challenges. In the Holy Quran, the primary responsibilities of individuals are examination and subservience. All of an individual's actions will be duly acknowledged and finalized in the hereafter, commencing upon their death.

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Human beings are comprised of earth and water, both literally and spiritually insufficient, vulnerable, and dependent. Nevertheless, in addition to possessing faculties such as intellect and volition, it is regarded as the most esteemed being in existence. Hence, to avoid the creator's benevolence being in vain, the individual was entrusted with several responsibilities, including the caliphate on earth, and was expected to carry out these obligations to the utmost perfection.

Humans possess not just a physical structure, but also a spiritual structure. Human beings possess both physical and spiritual attributes. According to Islamic texts, the soul is the faculty responsible for human awareness and movement. In the Holy Quran, the name Gabriel is also associated with angels, revelation, command, and judgment.

The topic of capturing the soul is mostly addressed in hadith literature, where the words "soul" and "nefs" are used instead of "spirit" as found in the Holy Quran.

Individuals possess psychological frameworks as well. The Holy Quran places significant emphasis on this facet of humanity. According to the statement, believers will not encounter any hardships or challenges during their soul's internment. However, it is said that unbelievers would have to undergo several problems that will hinder their ability to overcome this period easily. According to the Holy Quran, those who sacrifice their lives for noble principles do not experience death; instead, they continue to exist and are taken care of. In the Islamic religion, this term signifies "martyrdom". The reason for its usage was based on the observation that he led an elevated and selfless existence, ultimately giving up his life for it. However, humans are inherently social beings and as a result, they have cultivated a diverse range of connections. Death also engenders social connections in individuals' lives. Conversely, when an individual passes away, they undergo a shift and metamorphosis within the societal realm, triggering a process of loss and deprivation among those who were connected to the departed. Following the loss of a cherished individual, individuals

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may experience profound sorrow, undergo psychological phenomena, and engage in funeral customs. Engaging in rituals, such as reciting prayers, providing sustenance, and presenting indulgences to the bereaved, might be beneficial.

Our study findings indicate that Muslims adopt a mindset of perpetual remembrance of death, diligent preparation for death, a general lack of desire for death, and a willingness to endure death with patience. According to the words in which the Prophet said, "Die before you die," it implies that we should see death not as a mere fulfillment of our existence, but rather as the constant preparedness for judgment and mastery over the universe.

While the Holy Quran does not explicitly mention pain in the tomb, it is reasonable to acknowledge its presence based on the interpretations of scholars and reliable accounts.

The Holy Quran asserts that the apocalypse is an exceedingly dreadful and rapid event that will have a profound impact on both humanity and the cosmos. It underscores the certainty and truthfulness of this impending occurrence. The many phases of the afterlife, including Hashr, reckoning, paradise, and hell, are elucidated via illustrative tales that aim to facilitate comprehension among individuals. Simultaneously, there was an emphasis on the need to make preparations, acknowledging its correctness and the certainty of its occurrence.

Understanding death and the hereafter is crucial in one's existence. Having a clear grasp of both worldly life and death is equally crucial to having a right comprehension of the hereafter. Once an individual comprehends and grasps the concept of mortality and the underlying reason for their being in this realm, they will also get a comprehensive understanding of their own being. An individual who has self-awareness and self-identification may lead a life characterized by sound mental well-being, both in the present existence and in the hereafter.

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